

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

D1.2: Dataset on core trust items, climate science, and COVID-19

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ABSTRACT:	This document presents POIESIS' stock-taking strategy regarding the question how trust in science, research integrity and public integration are measured in surveys at the national and international level. It presents an initial set of comparable international core items in this regard as well as individualised national country reports and a literature review on empirical evidence of these concepts' interrelatedness.
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1 Introduction

The overarching research objective of POIESIS is to understand how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle.

Contributing to this objective, WP1 mainly addresses RQ1 of the project: **How can the nature and scale of public trust and mistrust in science be characterised and which are the factors that affect the relationship?** In this regard, it undertakes a stock-taking and analysis exercise based on relevant existing citizens' and scientists' surveys at the national and multi-/international level, complemented with expert workshops. The following sub-questions are the focus of WP1:

- What are the sources of public (mis)trust in science according to available evidence from the academic literature, previous EU projects, Eurobarometers, and national science barometers?
- How do levels of public (mis)trust in science compare across countries, disciplinary topics, and temporal periods according to the academic literature, previous EU projects, Eurobarometers, and national science barometers, and how can differences be associated with issues of integrity (e.g. cases of research misconduct) and integration (e.g. open science practices)?
- Which mechanisms connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
- What can existing evidence say about mechanisms for citizen co-creation of research and innovation and the role of 'chains of mediation' between research and citizens in relation to trust, and where do we currently lack sufficient understanding?

This document first provides a short overview on the conceptual framework of POIESIS and WP1's strategy for data exploration, collection, and analysis (see D1.1 for more details in this regard). Second, a curated set of core items for measuring 'trust in science' is presented aiming to provide an initial idea of levels of trust in science and attitudes on research integrity and public integration across countries and over time (without claiming to measure these concepts through these items, see chapter 2). The core item set is based on several waves of the Eurobarometer survey, the Wellcome Global Monitor, and the International Research Integrity Survey (IRIS).

To contextualise these core items further at the national level and to provide input for the empirical work of WP2 and WP3, short country reports follow for the countries of all POIESIS project partners (chapter 3). They are mainly based on relevant national surveys covering questions of trust in science, research integrity and public integration in the research process. In all surveys, special attention is paid to different contexts in which science might be presented. Of interest for us are science in general, climate change and science in the context of the coronavirus pandemic.

The fourth chapter contains the in D1.1 announced report on empirical evidence on relations between trust, integrity, and integration (see D1.1 section 3.2). Even if it is commonly assumed that the concepts of trust in science, research integrity and public integration in the research process are interrelated, empirical evidence of whether this is true or which mechanisms are at work in these interrelations is scarce. The here presented report is based on a literature review aiming to identify the most important empirical findings already existing in this regard.

1.1 Integrity, integration and institutions for trust – a conceptual model

POIESIS will concentrate on three core concepts: integrity, integration, and trust. Crucially, we will examine the interrelatedness of these concepts as well as the conditioning of these interrelations by institutions. Our conceptual model, which we call the ‘integrity, integration, and institutions for trust’ (3i4t) model, is graphically presented below. We consider integrity and integration as broad concepts facilitated by institutions, which through chains of mediation affect public trust in science.

Figure 1: The integrity, integration, and institutions for trust (3i4t) conceptual model

It is commonly assumed that issues related to research integrity and public integration in the research process affect public trust in science. Actual empirical evidence for these claims is, however, scarce. This is where POIESIS comes in: the project will not only analyse the public and expert perceptions of the project's core concepts – integrity, integration, and trust – but it will also scrutinise the role institutions play in this triangle. Its objective is to understand the mediating chains between integrity, integration, trust, and institutions, and how these dimensions relate to and affect each other. In other words, POIESIS aims to fill the arrows of the 3i4t model with content.

First, we aim to understand how citizens on the one hand and scientists on the other hand think about and relate to science in terms of trust, evaluating research integrity and (increased) public engagement in the research process. WP1 has started to address this task by taking stock of existing data streams covering these questions from the point of view of attitude surveys and curating and listing potentially relevant items in a shared dataset (see Appendices A and B). This structured dataset will continue to be nourished further throughout the entire course of the project.

1.2 Data exploration and data collection

As explained in WP1's protocol (see D1.1, section 2), all project partners have provided an initial list of national and international citizens' and scientists' surveys covering the following types of data:

Table 1: Different foci of indicators of trust, integrity, and integration

Topics/Aspects	Types of data	
	Representative citizens' public opinion data	(Representative) scientists' survey data
Attitudes to science in general	Direct and indirect indicators for citizens' trust in science	Scientists' awareness and evaluations of the public's attitudes towards science
Research integrity/ Responsible research and innovation	Citizens' awareness and evaluation of research integrity/Questionable research practices (QRPs)	Scientists' assessment of and attitudes towards research integrity/Questionable research practices (QRPs)
Integration/Public engagement in science	Citizens' attitudes towards public engagement in science (expectations, evaluation, behaviour)	Scientists' attitudes towards public engagement in science
Major public scandals	Recorded (national) breaches of integrity; only cases with a high level of public attention (threshold cases)	

All surveys containing questions that might help to get a hold of citizens' and scientists' different feelings of trust in science, and perceptions of research integrity and public integration have been listed in a shared dataset. Beyond the different types of data listed above, it has further been distinguished whether the object of trust is 'science' in a general sense or whether they are questions on science in the context of climate change and/or the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19). This list will be expanded and developed further over the course of the project (see also chapter 3).

In a first overview obtained on the content of these survey items, various ways of measuring and conceptualising the core concepts of interest for our project have been identified. All of them will gradually be collected and integrated in a synthesized dataset, allowing for an overview of available items across time and countries (see Table 2 in the next chapter). The content of this dataset will become the common basis for discussion among the project partners and in our expert workshops as well as for our analyses leading to the construction of indicators for trust in science, research integrity and public integration (D1.3).

As a first step of analysis and as a facilitating input for the empirical work of WP2 and WP3, a set of core items has been identified. It is intended to provide a first idea on the level of trust in science, and the understanding of research integrity and public integration in the countries of the local partners as far as this can be gauged with attitude surveys (without claiming to measure the concepts as such). It is presented in the following chapter.

2 The core items

The objectives of WP1 (D1.3) are to get an overview of existing measures of trust in science, as well as to develop sound indicators that measure levels of trust in science and attitudes towards research integrity and public integration. To this end, we developed a preliminary dataset containing a list of relevant surveys (see Appendix B) from which 'core items' were selected that aim to measure trust, integrity, and public integration across countries and over time. This dataset will be introduced below in Table 2 and expanded on in the following sub-sections. Importantly, this dataset will be growing over the duration of the POIESIS project and serve as a foundation upon which indicators of trust, integrity and integration can be constructed (D1.3).

The core items allow us to obtain a preliminary overview of public responses to questions relating to the concepts of integrity, integration and trust in the POIESIS partner countries. It is important to emphasise that we do not claim to measure the concepts of trust, integrity and integration as such through these items. The items we chose to present in this chapter relate to these concepts but were not constructed to measure them in the first place. For us, they serve the purpose of obtaining a first impression of what trust, integrity and integration mean for different people in different countries (and sometimes at different points in time). One of the future objectives of the POIESIS project is to come closer to ways of actually measuring trust, integrity and integration through appropriate indicators (D1.3).

Our core set of items also includes five different items related to attitudes to science, reflecting the classical three-dimensions (3D) of cognitive (knowledge, imagination, familiarity, psychological distance), affective-evaluative (utility and progress or moral concerns and reservations) and conative-motivational (approach-avoidance) aspects of the public's relationship to the world in general, and to science in particular (see Brentano, 1874; Rosenberg et al., 1960; Hilgard, 1980; Bauer & Suerdem, 2016). Items measuring these classical concepts happen to have the longest time-series in the Eurobarometer (EB) surveys reaching back to 1989. On a global scale they even reach back to the 1950s (Bauer & Falade, 2022). It is part of the challenges of POIESIS to examine how the more recent concerns about 'trust in science' and the older concerns about 'attitudes to science' are related, both conceptually and empirically.

The items that have been curated are presented in the structure of the new 'item dataset' in Table 2. Our current focus regarding the surveys is on several waves of Eurobarometer surveys, with a specific focus on EB95.2 (run in 2021), complemented by the international scientists' survey IRIS (run in 2021), and on the Wellcome Global Monitor (run in 2018 and 2020). These surveys are designed and implemented as internationally comparable base-line data. Additional or similar question items can also be found in citizen surveys organised at the national level and carried out at different points in time. Comparisons will therefore ultimately be possible at different levels: across countries and across time (see also chapter 3). The structure of the curated 'item dataset' as presented in Table 2 will facilitate the identification and actual realisation of such comparisons by visualising which items are available when and for which countries. Our growing database will curate additional sources of data for the purposes of indicator construction.

The following section 2.1 explains which items have been chosen and how they relate to the concepts of trust in science, research integrity and public integration. Section 2.2 then presents the empirical results of the questions in a comparative manner.

Table 2: Core items for trust in science, research integrity and public integration, listed in item dataset (citizens' surveys)¹

EB stands for Eurobarometer; WGM stands for Wellcome Global Monitor. In the table, 'x' indicates item scores that are available for that year; [i] indicates scores are imputed by extrapolation, i.e., by regression based on scores from previous years. The further contents of these items will be introduced and discussed in the next sub-sections. Appendix B lists the surveys referred to in this table, and many more.

	Year	2021	2020	2018	2013	2010	2005	2001	1992	1989
	Survey	EB95.2	WGM	WGM	EB79.2	EB73.1	EB63.1	EB55.2	EB38.1	EB31.0
Trust	deference	x								
	no option trust	x								
	industry money	x				x				
Integrity	open science	x								
	reliable	x								
	honest	x								
Integration	explain sufficiently	x								
	expected public engagement	x			x	x				
	talk	x				x				
	attend	x				x				
	take part	x				x				
Climate change	interest	x								
	cause of climate change	x								
COVID-19	vaccine index 2018			x						
	vaccine COVID		x							
	virus CT	x								
3D attitude	att1 life healthier [agree]	x			x	x	x	x	x	x
	att3 too fast [disagree]	x			x	x	x	x	x	x
	att2 faith [disagree]	x			x	x	x	x	x	x
	E sci int	x			[i]	x	x	x	x	x
	know13	x			[i]	[i]	x	x	x	x

¹ The dataset for the scientists' survey has a similar structure.

2.1 Selection and justification

The main objective of selecting a set of core items from international surveys with data for all POIESIS countries has been to obtain a first impression of available public and scientists' perceptions on trust in science, research integrity and public integration in the research process in general. To that we add questions in the specific context of climate change and COVID-19, the two topics that have been chosen as topical case studies for our project. In the following sub-sections, the items are listed and a short justification for their choice is provided. Section 2.2 presents the actual empirical data that are generated by these question items.

Our selection is unfolding the trust issue on four aspects: naming (1) the relationship between the (2) trustor, who 'does' the trusting, and the (3) trustee, who is the object of trust, and (4) some context modalities. In Table 3 we unfold this logic as a paradigm/syntagma structure, a logic that is further developing (Barthes, 1967). The paradigm in the vertical shows notions that are a replaceable in any of the four dimensions. We expect that each relevant 'trust item' in our database represents a sequence in the horizontal, i.e., a complete or incomplete path through these four dimensions. This logic allows to elegantly represent the actual diversity of measures of trust in science.

Table 3: Unfolding the logic of 'public trust' measures as a paradigm/syntagma

Naming the relation	Trustor (trust subject)	Trustee (trust object)	Context
Trust in; Is trustworthy; Truth telling (veracity); Confidence in; Doing a good job; Being familiar with; Attitude towards;	General public; Scientists	Science; Scientists; Industry researchers; General public; Integrity of science; Integration of public;	In general; Climate change; COVID-19

2.1.1 Trust in science

The first category of items includes questions that relate directly to citizens' trust in science. To indicate direct measures of trust we have unquestioned 'deference' to scientific authority, trust in the absence of any options (often called 'confidence' or 'no option trust'), and the item that indicates compromised authority of science, and therefore loss of trust, because of industrial funding.

Table 4: List of core items - trust in science

Item	Short name	Available in	Justification
<p>"The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly.</p> <p>Scientists ...know best what is good for people"</p>	deference	EB95.2 (2021): Q12a.10	Deference is a form of trust, maybe even an 'extreme' form; it hinges on exhibiting technocracy tolerance by deferring decisions to experts; data available in Eurobarometer surveys
<p>"We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology."</p>	no option trust	EB95.2 (2021): Q17.8	'No option' suggests that trust is granted without alternative, rendering this a confidence indicator; variance across countries is observed in Eurobarometer surveys; closely related to deference to technocrats
<p>"We can no longer trust scientists to tell the truth about controversial scientific and technological issues because they depend increasingly on money from industry."</p>	industry money	EB73.1 (2010): Q8.3 EB95.2 (2021): Q11.1	Loss of trust due to vested interest; reflection of trust having been the case, but no longer is; trusted authority resides in being able to display independent judgement, this is in jeopardy by industry funding; also related to research integrity

2.1.2 Research integrity (RI)

The second category of items relates to citizens' perception of research integrity (RI) which is an 'attribute of the object' of trust (trusting scientists to be X). This includes the desired characteristics of scientists and opinions on open science practices. Here we have two indicators: attributing virtues, scientists being seen to be reliable and honest. A third 'open access' indicator is a marker of scientists' transparency. This latter indicator is ambiguous: as well as research integrity, it could equally serve as an indicator for public integration, since openness and transparency of results, methods and data are preconditions of public integration (PI).

Table 5: List of core items – research integrity

Item		Short name	Available in	Justification
"The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly. [Scientists are...]"	...Reliable"	reliable	EB95.2 (2021): Q12a.1	Classic trustworthiness dimension; virtue attributed to scientists
	...Honest"	honest	EB95.2 (2021): Q12a.5	Classic trustworthiness dimension; virtue attributed to scientists
"The results of publicly funded research, such as scientific articles and data, should be made available online free of charge."		open science	EB79.2 (2013): QD17t EB95.2 (2021): Q9.5	Having expectations about open access science with regards to publication and research data, and being free of charge

2.1.3 Public integration (PI)

Concerning the public integration (PI) category, we distinguish between items relating to people's (1) normative expectations on public integration in the research process, (2) evaluations of the state of affairs, and (3) personal and actual active involvement in varying forms of participatory activities (scaling as levels of involvement). The public evaluates whether scientists sufficiently reach out and explain their research (Q9.3, 2021); the public has expectations as to the level of public engagement. This latter item is a choice of one-out-of-four. We report on the one that has larger variance and a higher normative expectation, namely the public demanding 'to be listened to and to be taken seriously'. Question 14 (EB95.2 2021) probes citizens' actual involvement on an escalating scale. From the twelve items, we curated three reflecting the lowest, middle, and highest levels of civic participation measured in this survey.

Table 6: List of core items – public integration

Item		Short name	Available in	Justification
"Scientists spend sufficient time meeting people like me to explain their work."		explain sufficiently	EB95.2 (2021): Q9.3	Providing information; expressing met or unmet expectations in that respect
"What level of public involvement do you think is appropriate when it comes to decisions about science and technology?"		expected public engagement: (listen + take seriously)	EB73.1 (2010): Q4 EB79.2 (2013): Q6 EB95.2 (2021): Q7	Level of public participation that is deemed desirable (item format: one-out-of-four)
"And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues. Do you..."	...Talk about science and technology-related issues with family or friends?"	talk	EB95.2 (2021): Q14.1	Lowest level of an escalating scale of civic participation
	...Attend public meetings or debates about science and technology?"	attend	EB95.2 (2021): Q14.6	Mid level of an escalating scale of civic participation
	...Actively take part in scientific projects by developing research questions, collecting data, discussing the findings with others, etc?"	take part	EB95.2 (2021): Q14.12	Highest level of an escalating scale of civic participation

2.1.4 Climate change

The core items for the specific context of climate change relate to citizens' interest in the topic and their belief in the causes of climate change – these items therefore indirectly indicate trust in science. As such, these two items provide an initial gauge of people's perception of science related to climate change.

Table 7: List of core items – climate change

Item	Short name	Available in	Justification
<p>“In everyday life, we have to deal with many different problems and situations, where we feel more or less interested and confident. I am going to read you a number of statements. For each of them, please tell me whether you are interested [in...]</p> <p>...Environmental problems including climate change.”</p>	interest	<p>EB73.1 (2010): Q1.4</p> <p>EB95.2 (2021): Q2.6</p>	Issue discrimination; rating climate change in a list of other potential interests
<p>“Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so.</p> <p>Climate change is for the most part caused by natural cycles rather than human activities.” (false = correct)</p>	cause of climate change	EB95.2 (2021): Q9.3	Recognising human causality on climate change; if denied can be an index of 'conspiratorial mentality'

2.1.5 COVID-19 / Vaccines

The coronavirus pandemic of 2020/21 is the most recent topic we will be dealing with in our project. Trust has been approached from different angles in varying surveys, mostly with questions on trust in governmental decisions and in their handling of the pandemic. For an initial assessment of how people feel about science in the context of COVID-19, we chose citizens' opinion on vaccines and their belief (or not) in the nefarious human design of viruses, an item that borders on 'conspiratorial mentality'.

Table 8: List of core items – COVID-19

Item		Short name	Available in	Justification
"Do you agree, disagree, or neither agree nor disagree with the following statement?"	"Vaccines are important for children to have."	Pre-COVID vaccine index 2018 [index = being undecided or disagreeing with any of these three statements]	WGM 2018: Q24	Pre-COVID index of vaccine hesitancy on three dimensions: importance, safety, and effectiveness
	"Vaccines are safe."		WGM 2018: Q25	
	"Vaccines are effective."		WGM 2018: Q26	
"Vaccines are given to people to help prevent specific diseases. If a vaccine to prevent coronavirus was available right now at no cost, would you agree to be vaccinated?"		vaccine COVID-19 [% agree]	WGM 2020: WP21768	Vaccine hesitancy during COVID-19, but measured before vaccines were available
"Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so. Viruses have been produced in government laboratories to control our freedom." [false = correct]		vaccine CT	EB95.2 (2021): Q20.11	Vaccine items that might indicate knowledge of vaccines, but also conspiratorial mentality if agreed to

2.1.6 Attitudes to science

The items related to attitudes to science are the ones for which the longest time-series are available in the Eurobarometer surveys reaching back to 1989 for EU12 countries. They therefore enable an assessment of the evolution of the public's relationship to science over time in terms of attitude. Because of the complexity of their display, the empirical results of these items are presented per country in chapter 3 and not in a comparative perspective in section 2.2 as the other core items. How attitudes in science are related to trust in science is both a conceptual and an empirical challenge for this project. An initial hunch might arise from interpreting attitudes as features of trustworthiness competence and integrity. Being interested in science and being familiar with it reflects degrees of integration with science.

Table 9: List of core items – attitudes to science

Item	Short name	Available in	Justification
S&T makes our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable	att1 health [agree]	EB31.0 (1989) EB38.1 (1992) EB55.2 (2001) EB63.1 (2005) EB73.1 (2010) EB79.2 (2013) EB95.2 (2021)	utility outcome, [competence trust]
S&T make our lives change too fast	att3 too fast [disagree]		value related concern; [integrity]
We depend too much on science and not enough on faith	att2 faith [disagree]		value related concern, [integrity]
How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?	sci interest [interested]		interest, engagement, [integration]
Various knowledge quiz items [true/false]	knowledge index		familiarity with science, [integration]

2.1.7 Scientists' perspective

Scientists – those mostly affected when citizens no longer trust in science – might have different views on how important this trust actually is and why one should care about research integrity. For scientists, public trust is an intangible asset to which they variously pay attention to. Two items from the IRIS survey have been chosen for an initial idea in this regard. They represent the causal link from research integrity => quality of research => securing public trust.

Table 10: List of core items – scientists' perspective

Item	Short name	Available in	Justification
“Do you think that research integrity policies help to improve the quality of your research?”	improve	IRIS 2021: improve	Scientists’ views about the importance of research integrity; a quality indicator of research and/or the research process
“And now, how motivating would each of the following factors be in encouraging you to adhere to formal research integrity procedures? ...More trust in my research by the general public.”	motivation trust	IRIS 2021: mtvtrstpub	Securing public trust of the public is a core motivation for researcher integrity

2.2 Presentation of results

This section presents empirical data related to the core items introduced above in a comparative perspective across countries and – if possible – over time. The visualisations in this section display a selection of the available data. The full tables upon which this sub-section’s graphs are based, are available in Appendix A. In these tables, extra categories are included which, for example, group questionnaires’ answers together (indicated by light grey columns). For example, ‘Strongly agree’ and ‘Tend to agree’ are summed up in the category ‘Agree’. These categories are occasionally used for the purposes of comparison in the below graphs.

In every graph, the seven partner countries of POIESIS are denominated by their most common abbreviations: Germany (DE), Denmark (DK), Spain (ES), France (FR), Greece (GR), Portugal (PT), and the United Kingdom (UK). Further, the average results from all participating countries in every Eurobarometer wave are presented (EU+), as well as the average results from all participating countries in the IRIS scientists’ survey (denominated by ‘IRIS average’).

2.2.1 Trust in science

Figure 2: Trust item - deference

QA12a.10 (EB95.2; 2021): “The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly. [Scientists] know best what is good for people.”

- Possible answers: Describes well / Describes badly / Don’t know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by ‘Describes well’.

Figure 3: Trust item – no option trust

QA17.8 (EB95.2; 2021): “How strongly do you agree or disagree with the following [statement]? We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.”

- Possible answers: Strongly agree / Tend to agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Tend to disagree / Strongly disagree / Don’t know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by ‘Agree’.

Figure 4: Trust item – industry money

This item was asked twice: in EB73.1 (2010) and EB95.2 (2021). The graph below visualises their results and is rank ordered on ‘Agree (2021)’.

Q8.3 (EB73.1; 2010): “To what extent do you agree with the following statements? We can no longer trust scientists to tell the truth about controversial scientific and technological issues because they depend more and more on money from industry.”

- Possible answers: Totally agree / Tend to agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Tend to disagree / Totally disagree / Don’t know.

QA11.1 (EB95.2; 2021): “To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding scientists today? We can no longer trust scientists to tell the truth about controversial scientific and technological issues because they depend increasingly on money from industry.”

- Possible answers: Totally agree / Tend to agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Tend to disagree / Totally disagree / Don’t know.

2.2.2 Research integrity

Figure 5: Integrity item – *reliable / honest*

QA12a (EB95.2; 2021): “The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly.”

- QA12a.1: Reliable; QA12a.5: Honest
- Possible answers: Describes well / Describes badly / Don’t know.
- Data in graphs are rank ordered by ‘Describes well’.

Figure 6: Integrity item – *open science*

QD17t (EB79.2; 2013): “Do you think that the results of publicly funded research should be made available online free of charge?”

- Possible answers: Yes, to the general public / Yes, to other researchers / Yes, to industries / No / Don't know.
- Data in graphs is rank ordered by 'Total 'Yes''.

QA9.5 (EB95.2; 2021): “The following are some statements that people have made about science or technology. For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree. The results of publicly funded research, such as scientific articles and data, should be made available online free of charge.”

- Possible answers: Strongly agree / Tend to agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Tend to disagree / Strongly disagree / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Agree'.

2.2.3 Public integration

Figure 7: Integration item – explain sufficiently

QA9.3 (EB95.2; 2021): “The following are some statements that people have made about science or technology. For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree. Scientists spend sufficient time meeting people like me to explain their work.”

- Possible answers: Strongly agree / Tend to agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Tend to disagree / Strongly disagree / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Agree' (grouping together 'Strongly agree' and 'Tend to agree').

Figure 8: Integration item – expected public engagement

This item featured in EB73.1, EB79.2 and EB95.2, thus allowing for comparison across the years. Notably, the phrasing of the question as well as its possible answers had slight variations across the years, yet they can be considered synonymous. Please see Appendix A for the possible phrasings of all answers to each question, as well as their distributions. The data in Figure 8 below is rank ordered from high to low for the year 2021.

QC4 (EB73.1; 2010): “Which of the following public involvement [sic] do you think is appropriate when it comes to decisions about science and technology?”

- Answer selected for graph: “The public should be consulted and public opinion should only be considered when making decisions about science and technology.”

QD6 (EB79.2; 2013): “What is the level of involvement citizens should have when it comes to decisions made about science and technology?”

- Answer selected for graph: “Citizens should be consulted and their opinion should be considered.”

QA7 (EB95.2; 2021): “What level of public involvement do you think is appropriate when it comes to decisions about science and technology?”

- Answer selected for graph: “The public should be consulted and public opinion should be seriously considered when making decisions about science and technology.”

Figure 9: Integration item – talk / attend / take part

This question measures public engagement on an escalating scale, ranging from low engagement (question 1) to high engagement (question 12). For the current purposes, three questions (1, 6 and 12) were chosen to gauge public engagement at different levels.

QA14 (EB95.2; 2021): “And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues. Do you...

... (1) Talk about science and technology-related issues with family or friends?”

... (6) Attend public meetings or debates about science and technology?”

... (12) Actively take part in scientific projects by developing research questions, collecting data, discussing the findings with others, etc?”

- Possible answers to all questions: Yes, regularly / Yes, occasionally / Hardly ever / No, never / Don't know.
- Data in graphs are rank ordered by 'Yes, regularly'.

2.2.4 Climate change

Figure 10: Climate change item – interest

QC1 (EB73.1; 2010): “In everyday life, we have to deal with many different problems and situations, where we feel more or less interested and confident. I am going to read you a number of statements. For each of them, please tell me whether you are [interested in...] Environmental problems.”

- Possible answers: Very interested / Moderately interested / Not at all interested / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Very interested'.

QA2.6 (EB95.2; 2021): “In everyday life, we have to deal with many different issues, where we feel more or less interested. For each of the following, please indicate whether you are [interested in...] Environmental problems including climate change.”

- Possible answers: Very interested / Moderately interested / Not at all interested / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Very interested'.

Figure 11: Climate change item – cause of climate change

QA20.9 (EB95.2; 2021): “Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so. Climate change is for the most part caused by natural cycles rather than human activities.”

- Possible answers: True / False / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'False' (correct).

2.2.5 COVID-19/Vaccines

Figure 12: COVID-19 item – virus conspiracy theory (CT)

QA20.11 (EB95.2; 2021): “Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so. Viruses have been produced in government laboratories to control our freedom.”

- Possible answers: True / False / Don't know.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'False' (correct).

Figure 13: COVID-19 item – vaccine index 2018

WGM 2018 vaccine hesitancy index

Q24: “Do you agree, disagree, or neither agree nor disagree with the following statement? Vaccines are important for children to have.”

Q25: “Do you agree, disagree, or neither agree nor disagree with the following statement? Vaccines are safe.”

Q26: “Do you agree, disagree, or neither agree nor disagree with the following statement? Vaccines are effective.”

- Possible answers: (If agree) Do you strongly agree or somewhat agree? (If disagree) Do you strongly or somewhat disagree?
- In the graphic the index is rank ordered, such that the highest scores reflect the most vaccine hesitancy (binary index; 1 = expressing neither/nor or disagreement with any of the three statements). Data for all European countries are presented; POIESIS partner countries are marked in orange.

Figure 14: COVID-19 item – vaccine COVID-19

WP21768 WGM 2020: “Vaccines are given to people to help prevent specific diseases. If a vaccine to prevent coronavirus was available right now at no cost, would you agree to be vaccinated?”

- Possible answers: Yes, would agree / No, would not agree / Don’t know.
- Rank-ordered such that the highest scores reflect the most COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy (i.e., answered ‘No, would not agree’).

2.2.6 Scientists' perspective

Figure 15: Scientists item – improve

improve (IRIS, 2022): “Do you think that research integrity policies help to improve the quality of your research?”

- Possible answers: Always improve the quality of my research / Mostly improve the quality of my research / Sometimes improve the quality of my research / Rarely improve the quality of my research / Never improve the quality of my research.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Always/mostly' (grouping together the first two answers).

Figure 16: Scientists item – motivation trust

mtvtrstpub (IRIS, 2022): “And now, how motivating would each of the following factors be in encouraging you to adhere to formal research integrity procedures? More trust in my research by the general public.”

- Possible answers: Not at all motivating / Somewhat motivating / Fairly motivating / Very motivating / Extremely motivating.
- Data in graph is rank ordered by 'Very/Extremely' (grouping together the final two answers).

3 National reports

The presentation of the core items in a comparable perspective has revealed interesting first insights into people's approach towards trust in science, research integrity and public integration in the countries of the project partners and beyond. In order to further contextualise these attitudes in each of the POIESIS countries, the following chapter shortly presents questions with a similar focus from (mostly) national citizens' surveys.

During the data collection process, all project partners provided lists of national and international surveys that might include questions in relation to different foci of indicators of trust, integrity and integration (see Appendix B). They were asked to collect information including the name of the survey (wave), the year(s) in which it has been carried out, the author or organisation behind the survey, whether it is available in English, and whether questionnaires, raw data and reports or analyses are available. Questions of interest concern for example citizens' and scientists' attitudes towards science, research integrity, and public integration in general, but also more specifically in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and climate change (see Table 1 in section 1.2). These sources will be analysed thoroughly in POIESIS' task 1.3, leading ultimately to the development of sound indicators for measuring trust in science, research integrity and public integration (D1.3).

The currently presented national reports are the result of an initial assessment of potential data sources and shall be considered a starting point for more detailed analysis. They will further serve as input material for the empirical work of WP2 and WP3. The reports are mainly based on national surveys, or, in case that not much national data on relevant questions is (yet) available, further international surveys on related topics. Indeed, the availability of relevant data varies considerably across countries, leading to divergent bases for analysis in the different contexts and obviously also very different contents of the national reports.

We present questions related to citizens' attitudes towards trust in science, research integrity and public integration in general or in the context of COVID-19 and climate change. The choice has been made to select items that are rather different from the core items presented above (see chapter 2) in order to provide a more complex picture of predominant attitudes in the single countries. Next, comparable items from the Eurobarometer and national surveys will be contrasted, once again in the process towards the development of indicators for trust in science, research integrity and public integration.

All country reports start with the presentation of the set of core items related to *attitudes to science* for which the longest timelines can be drawn from the Eurobarometer data (see section 2.1.6). Because of their complexity, they are shown here individually for each country rather than in a comparative perspective in the previous chapter. The attitude items are scored on a T-transformation with $M=500$ and $SD=100$; the mean and SD are the pooled EU12 average for each item between 1989 and 2005 [Don't-Knows for Likert scales are coded into the middle category of N/N]. Note that all items are coded so that a higher score indicates a move in a 'direction towards science': more knowledge, more interest, higher expectations, lesser concerns. Knowledge scores for each year reflect sums of the 'correct' responses to knowledge-based questions. For 2010 and 2013, where we have no knowledge items, we imputed scores on the linear trend between 1989-2005 and estimated a score for 2010 and 2013. In 2021, we have only six knowledge items rather than thirteen as in previous years, so we extrapolated scores to a scale of k13. The interest scores for 2013 are equally extrapolated. Note that the raw data for some figures presented below are not available, in such case, figures were retrieved from the original survey and presented in the same way as in the original reports, amongst others implying that they might be in the original study's language.

Once again, it shall be noted that the here presented survey questions do not as such measure the concepts of trust in science, research integrity and public integration but merely relate to them (see also Chapter 2).

3.1 Denmark

In Denmark, there are four (waves of) surveys relevant to our research interest, the oldest one dating back to the late 1990s: the Folk og Forskning surveys, conducted in 1997 and 2000; the Gallup surveys from 2007, 2011 and 2014; the Operate 2020 from 2020 and a short one, Befolkningsmåling, from 2017. The items presented here have been drawn from reports of the first three of these surveys (detailed references for all surveys can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions provide more insights on what people in Denmark think about trust in science in general, research integrity and public integration in the research process.

3.1.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 17 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in Denmark from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science were settled rather around the European average (M=500) in Denmark in the 1990s. Since then, all items have risen above European average, particularly the knowledge index and even more the rejection of the statement “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith”.

Figure 17: Attitudes to science in Denmark

att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
 att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
 att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
 sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
 k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.1.2 Trust in science

This section on trust in science in Denmark shows data from the Folk og Forskning surveys 1997 and 2000, the Gallup survey 2014 and the Wellcome Global Monitor 2018, an international survey comparing people’s opinions and feelings about science and health related issues around the world.

Table 11 shows that most Danes feel moderate confidence towards researchers and that the share of people with high confidence has decreased between 1997 and 2000. Young people indicate the highest confidence in researchers, as much in 1997 as in 2000.

Table 11: Trust in researchers by age and over time in Denmark

	16-29 years		30-59 years		60-85 years		I total	
	1997	2000	1997	2000	1997	2000	1997	2000
Low confidence	15	17	16	26	25	32	18	25
Medium confidence	63	69	66	63	55	56	62	63
High confidence	22	14	18	11	20	12	20	12
I total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
N	304	272	762	799	313	270	1379	1341

Source: Folk og Forskning 2001

Figure 18: Trust in science by sociodemographic variables in Denmark

Q5: To what extent do you generally trust the research carried out in Denmark?

Source: TNS Gallup 2014

In Figure 18 above, data from the TNS Gallup survey indicates that either the situation has changed significantly between 2000 and 2014, or that people respond differently to the question whether they trust research carried out in Denmark (compared to trust in researchers, see above). 35% of respondents indicate that they trust research in Denmark to a high degree and 56% to some extent. People over the age of 60 have the largest share of respondents with particularly high trust in Danish research.

And finally, Table 12 shows that the Danish citizens lead by far in the international comparison of what the Wellcome Global Monitor calls “Science Enthusiasts”, referring to people who are convinced that the work of scientists benefits themselves but also most people of their country.

Table 12: Percentage of »Science Enthusiasts« in Denmark (in comparison)

Countries where people are most likely to be science ‘Enthusiasts’

Percentage of people who said science benefits people like them and most people in the country.

Do you think the work that scientists do benefits most, some or very few people in this country?

In general, do you think the work that scientists do benefits people like you in this country?

Country	% Enthusiasts
Denmark	75%
Iceland	61%
Finland	61%
Saudi Arabia	55%
China, Greece, Uzbekistan	54%

Source: Wellcome Global Monitor 2018 (Table 4.2)

3.1.3 Research integrity

Not many questions could be identified in the Danish national surveys that may relate to the concept of research integrity. On the tipping point between being a question of trust or rather research integrity, the survey Operate 2020 finds that the statement “Scientists cannot be trusted because they are subject to political or economic interests” is among the ones Danes agree least with. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is “strongly disagree”, Danes reach 2.6 on average for this statement.

3.1.4 Public integration

There are not many questions related to public integration in the research process in Danish national surveys, but Figure 19 shows that a majority of people stated in 2014 that it should be up to companies and universities to decide on the topics of research in Denmark. The share of people thinking that the population, politicians, or public researchers should strongly be involved in the decision-making process has strongly decreased between 2007 and 2014. More and more people also state that they do not know the answer to this question.

Figure 19: Desired actors of decision-making in research in Denmark

Q4: Who do you think should decide what research is done in Denmark? Is it...? (More marks possible)

Source: TNS Gallup 2014

3.2 France

For France, the list of available surveys relevant to our research interest is long. It comprises 12 (waves of) surveys, covering a period from 1972 to 2023. Several of these surveys are specifically dedicated to questions concerning the French citizens’ opinion on science and its role in society. The items presented here have been drawn from the brochure and detailed research report of the survey wave “Les Français et la Science”, regrouping the results of eight surveys conducted on the French perception towards science since 1972 (detailed references for these documents can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions provide more insights on what people in France think about trust in science in general, in the context of the coronavirus pandemic, and about public integration in the research process.

3.2.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 20 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in France from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science were settled around or closely above the European average (M=500) in France in the 1990s. While especially the interest in new scientific discoveries as well as the approval of the statement “Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable” have decreased compared to the European average over time, knowledge in scientific matters but also the opinion that we do not depend too much on science compared to faith are far above European average now.

Figure 20: Attitudes to science in France

att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
 att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
 att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
 sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
 k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.2.2 Trust in science

This section on trust in science in France shows two figures from the brochure “Les Français et la Science” published in 2021. In Figure 21, we see the evolution of answers to the question “Do you trust or distrust science?” in France since 2001. While the share of respondents indicating not to trust science (not much and not at all) remains relatively stable over time, fewer people indicate to have a lot of trust in science in 2020 compared to the years before. There are also more and more people stating not to have an opinion on this question.

Figure 21: Trust in science in France over time

Source: Enquêtes «Les Français et la Science», 2001-2020 / N3033 (en 2020), brochure

Figure 22 shows how French citizens responded to the question whether they have the impression that science does humanity more good than harm or the other way around since 1972. To contextualise the figure further, French presidencies and important societal events during this period have been added to the figure. In broad terms, it appears that respondents in the 1970s and 1980s perceived the benefits of science for humanity to be higher than today. Until 1982, the majority of people indicated that science does more good than harm. Since then, always more than 50% of the people said it was rather equal. Between 2011 and 2020, the share of people believing strongly in the benefits of science has sharply decreased at the same time as those thinking that science actually does more harm than good has risen above 10% for the first time since 1972.

Figure 22: Benefit of science in France over time

D'une manière générale, avez-vous l'impression que la science apporte à l'homme...
 Generally speaking, do you have the impression that science does humanity...

Sources : enquêtes « Les Français et la Science », 1972-2020 / N 3033 (en 2020)

Source: Enquêtes «Les Français et la Science», 2001-2020 / N3033 (en 2020), brochure

3.2.3 COVID-19

The most recent survey reported in the brochure of “Les Français et la Science” has been carried out in 2020 and included a question on trust in different public actors in the context of the coronavirus pandemic. Figure 23 shows the results of this question. French citizens mostly trust doctors to tell the truth about the virus, followed by scientists and the WHO. Journalists, politicians and religious leaders enjoy only very low levels of trust in the context of COVID-19: only 2% of respondents indicate that they trust politicians a lot to tell the truth about the coronavirus; 25% trust them a little.

Figure 23: Trust in public actors in the context of COVID-19 in France

À l’occasion de la crise du coronavirus, on a beaucoup parlé des « fake news » ou des « infox », de fausses informations. Dans quelle mesure faites-vous confiance aux personnes suivantes pour vous dire la vérité sur le coronavirus ?
 During the coronavirus crisis, there has been a lot of talk about « fake news », false information. How much do you trust the following to tell you the truth about the coronavirus?

Source: Enquête »Les Français et la Science«, 2020 / N3033 (en 2020), brochure

3.2.4 Public integration

Table 13 shows a question related to the concept of public integration in the scientific process, addressed to French citizens four times since 1972. Respondents were asked to indicate who in their opinion has the strongest influence on the orientation of scientific and technological research. Until 2011, most people answered “the government” to this question. In 2020, however, 42% of respondents think that it is scientific researchers deciding on the direction of scientific and technological research. People also perceive the influence of private companies to have risen over time. Only very few respondents think that it is the population who has the most important say in this. Their share remains rather stable over the decades.

Table 13: Perceived actors of decision-making in research in France over time

France, 1972-2020, (% colonne)	1972 N : 1 200	1982 N : 1 515	2011 N : 1 027	2020 N : 3 033
Influence sur l'orientation de la recherche scientifique et technique				
Le gouvernement	37%	46%	35%	23%
Les chercheurs scientifiques	33%	24%	27%	42%
Les entreprises privées	11%	6%	21%	21%
Les militaires	6%	5%	8%	2%
L'ensemble de la population	3%	3%	4%	2%
Les entreprises nationalisées		3%		
Sans opinion	10%	13%	5%	10%

Source: Enquête «Les Français et la Science», 2020 / N3033 (Table 7), rapport de recherche

3.3 Germany

In Germany, the Wissenschaftsbarometer is the most prominent survey when it comes to polling the attitudes of German citizens towards science and research. It has been conducted yearly since 2014 and the items presented here have been drawn from the most recent reports presenting their results (detailed references for the documents can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). Apart from the Wissenschaftsbarometer, the TechnikRadar, carried out on a yearly basis since 2018, also provides insights into science- and technology-related opinions of the German population. After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions give a short overview about what people in Germany think about trust in science in general, in the context of the coronavirus pandemic in particular, and about the issue of research integrity.

3.3.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 24 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in Germany from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science centred closely around the European average (M=500) in Germany in the 1990s but have spread considerably since then. The knowledge index for German citizens has steadily increased and is particularly high in the latest survey round of 2021. The same applies to the rejection of the statement “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith”. Compared to the European average, fewer Germans think that “Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable” today, following a strong decline after 2005.

Figure 24: Attitudes to science in Germany

att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
 att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
 att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
 sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
 k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Note: Observations on Germany pre-2001 are only for West Germany [BRD] as only post-2001 EU data reflects the fact of German unification and the end of the Cold War.

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.3.2 Trust in science

Insights on German citizens' opinion on trust in science are provided here by means of two questions retrieved from the reports of the Wissenschaftsbarometer 2021 and 2022. Figure 25 shows how answers to the question "How much do you trust science and research" have evolved in Germany since 2017. A considerable increase in the level of trust towards science (trust completely and trust somewhat) can be observed with the beginning of the coronavirus pandemic in 2020. This increase comes with a drop of respondents undecided about their level of trust towards science. The number of those distrusting science has remained rather stable.

Figure 25: Trust in science in Germany over time

How much do you trust science and research?

Numbers for „don't know, missing answer" not shown; Minimum of 1.000 respondents each survey wave; Figures are in per cent. Numbers may not add up to 100 per cent due to rounding.

- trust completely / trust somewhat
- undecided
- distrust somewhat / distrust completely

Source: Wissenschaftsbarometer 2022

Figure 26: Benefit of science in Germany over time

Scientists work for the benefit of society.

Source: Wissenschaftsbarometer 2021

Above, in Figure 26, we can see that the approval of the statement “Scientists work for the benefit of society” in 2021 in Germany is comparable to the one in 2017 (in 2019 fewer people agreed with it). Similar as for the question of trust, many respondents are undecided on this matter as well.

3.3.3 COVID-19

Since the beginning of the coronavirus pandemic, the Wissenschaftsbarometer included questions on people’s attitudes towards the role of science and scientists in the context of this crisis. Figure 27 shows the approval and disapproval of several statements with regard to the coronavirus pandemic of respondents in 2020 and 2021. A large majority of people is convinced that the coronavirus exists. However, opinions differ strongly regarding the questions how the virus should be handled and even more whether scientists do or do not “tell us everything they know about the coronavirus”.

Figure 27: Attitudes towards coronavirus pandemic in Germany

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Scientists do not tell us everything they know about the coronavirus.

The coronavirus pandemic is being made into a bigger deal than it actually is.

We should rely more on common sense when dealing with the coronavirus pandemic and we do not need any scientific studies for this.

There is no real proof that the coronavirus really exists.

Minimum of 1.000 respondents each survey wave; Figures are in per cent. Numbers may not add up to 100 per cent due to rounding.

● completely agree
 ● somewhat agree
 ● undecided
● somewhat disagree
 ● completely disagree
● don't know, missing answer

Source: Wissenschaftsbarometer 2021

3.3.4 Research integrity

Figure 28 shows data from the Wissenschaftsbarometer on the approval and disapproval of several potential reasons why to trust or distrust scientists, as well as their evolution over time. These two questions and their different answer categories are at the tipping point between the concepts of trust in science and research integrity. They therefore represent a good example of the disentangling exercise POIESIS needs to carry out to provide clarity in this regard. Generally speaking, more and more respondents agree with all three reasons to trust scientists, but also the approval of reasons for distrust has re-increased since 2020. The most prominent reason for trusting scientists is and has always been their expertise, followed by them working according to rules and standards. The most important reason for distrust continues to be the scientists' dependence on the funders of their research.

Figure 28: Reasons for trust and distrust towards scientists in Germany over time

Agreement with different reasons to trust scientists

Aggregated numbers for 'somewhat agree' and 'completely agree' shown;
Minimum of 1,000 respondents each survey wave;
Figures are in per cent. Numbers may not add up to 100 per cent due to rounding.

Agreement with different reasons to distrust scientists

Aggregated numbers for 'somewhat agree' and 'completely agree' shown;
Minimum of 1,000 respondents each survey wave;
Figures are in per cent. Numbers may not add up to 100 per cent due to rounding.

Source: Wissenschaftsbarometer 2022

3.4 Greece

In Greece, the available surveys relevant to our research interest are very recent, namely from 2020 (Καταγραφή των απόψεων της κοινής γνώμης σχετικά με την πανδημία του COVID 19), 2021 (Πανελλαδική Έρευνα Κοινής Γνώμης για την Πανδημία του Κορωνοϊού) and 2022 (Πανελλαδική Έρευνα για την Κλιματική Αλλαγή). The first two focus on public attitudes in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and the third one on the topic of climate change. The here presented questions therefore focus on these topics, supplemented by data from the Wellcome Global Monitor 2018, an international survey comparing people’s opinions and feelings about science and health related issues around the world, for the trust in science section (detailed references for the surveys can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). The report starts with the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2.

3.4.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 29 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in Greece from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science have seen a considerable evolution since 1989 in Greece. While having been spread rather far around the European average (M=500) in the 1980s and 1990s, most of them are now settled closer around it. An exception to this is the item “Science and technology make our lives change too fast”: less people than in other European countries disagree with this in Greece today. They also think more often that “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith” than respondents in other countries.

Figure 29: Attitudes to science in Greece

- att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
- att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
- att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
- sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
- k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.4.2 Trust in science

As no national survey data is available providing insights about the Greek citizens' trust in science, data from the Wellcome Global Monitor is mobilised here. Figure 30 shows that Greece is among the countries in which people are most often likely to say that the work of scientists does benefit most people in their country.

Figure 30: Benefit of science in Greece (in comparison)

Countries where people are more likely to say the work that scientists do benefit most people in their country

Percentage of people who answered 'most', 'some', 'very few' or 'don't know/refused'.

Do you think that the work that scientists do benefits most, some or very few people in this country?

Source: Wellcome Global Monitor 2018 (Chart 4.4)

3.4.3 COVID-19

The strong opinions Greek citizens express towards science is also reflected in their answer to the question how much they trust the committee of experts monitoring the course of the coronavirus pandemic (Figure 31, Interview 2020 survey). A huge majority of respondents indicates that they do trust this committee quite or very much.

Figure 31: Trust in times of COVID-19 in Greece

How much confidence do you have in the committee of experts (infectious disease specialists, epidemiologists) who are monitoring the course of the pandemic and proposing measures?

Source: Interview 2020

3.4.4 Climate change

Data from a survey carried out by Dianeosis in 2022 (Figure 32) shows that citizens in Greece perceive the climate change crisis today as a very important issue. 32.1% of respondents scored the seriousness of the climate change crisis with the highest possible answer category (10). Nearly 70% of respondents chose a score between 8 and 10 (very serious).

Figure 32: Perceived seriousness of the climate change crisis today in Greece (on a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 is »not serious at all« and 10 is »very serious«)

Source: Dianeosis 2022 (Figure 7)

3.5 Portugal

In Portugal, the few existent public surveys relevant to our research interest date back to the 2000s: the Ministério da Ciência e da Tecnologia organised two survey rounds in 1997 and 2000 (Relatório do Inquérito a Cultura Científica dos Portugueses) and the ISCTE institute another one in 2000 (Publicos da Ciencia em Portugal). Additionally, there has been a survey concerning public attitudes towards COVID-19 with two waves in 2020. The data for these surveys is not publicly available; we are still in the collection process. For now, this report therefore relies on data from international surveys, namely the Wellcome Global Monitor, an international survey comparing people’s opinions and feelings about science and health related issues around the world, and different waves of the Eurobarometer. After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions give a short impression of what people in Portugal think about trust in science in general and public integration in the research process.

3.5.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 33 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in Portugal from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science were settled closely to the European average (M=500) in Portugal in the 1990s. Interest in scientific discoveries and the knowledge index were rather low but have strongly increased since then, being situated far above European average in 2021. The disapproval of the statement “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith” has equally involved from below to far beyond European average over time.

Figure 33: Attitudes to science in Portugal

- att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
- att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
- att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
- sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
- k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.5.2 Trust in science

The “trust in science” section uses data from the Wellcome Global Monitor 2018 with a question on trust in scientists, and the latest Eurobarometer survey on attitudes towards science from 2021 with an item on the perceived personal benefit of science. Table 14 shows that Portugal is among the 12 countries in the worldwide comparison of the Wellcome Global Monitor in which people are most likely to put high trust in scientists. More than half of the respondents further indicate that they have moderate trust in scientists. However, the share of people with low trust is, with 11%, also relatively high compared to the other countries in the ranking.

Table 14: Trust in scientists in Portugal (in comparison)

Trust in Scientists Index showing countries where people most likely to have high trust

Countries with the highest percentage of people in the 'high' trust (30% of people and above).

Wellcome Global Monitor Trust in Scientists Index.

	High trust	Medium trust	Low trust	No opinion
Uzbekistan	54%	38%	2%	6%
Belgium	42%	48%	8%	2%
Tajikistan	42%	41%	9%	8%
Niger	39%	30%	14%	17%
Spain	39%	54%	6%	1%
Ireland	39%	55%	5%	1%
Norway	38%	59%	3%	1%
United Kingdom	35%	55%	9%	1%
Finland	35%	58%	7%	0%
Malta	34%	53%	7%	6%
Portugal	34%	54%	11%	2%
The Gambia	34%	42%	11%	13%

Source: Wellcome Global Monitor 2018

In Table 15, data from the Eurobarometer survey indicates that most people in Portugal are convinced that science and technology do benefit them personally: the disagreement with the statement “Science and technology do not really benefit people like you” is very high (67.8% tend to or strongly disagree).

Table 15: Personal benefit of science in Portugal

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
Science and technology do not really benefit people like you.	3.4%	13.5%	15.3%	43.2%	24.6%	0%

Source: Eurobarometer survey 95.2 (2021)

3.5.1 Public integration

Two items from the Eurobarometer surveys (EB63.1 in 2005 and EB95.2 in 2021) provide an idea about the Portuguese opinion on public integration in the research process. Table 16 shows that in 2005, respondents were rather divided on the question whether the public was sufficiently involved in scientific decisions; a majority, however, disagreed with this statement. In 2021, most people agreed or even strongly agreed with the societal benefits of involving non-scientists in research and technological developments.

Table 16: Opinions on public integration in decision-making in science in Portugal

	Wave	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree
The public is sufficiently involved in decisions about science and technology.	EB63.1 (2005)	7.1%	21.7%	17.2%	24.6%	29.4%
Involving non-scientists in research and technological development ensures that science and technology respond to the needs, values and expectations of society.	EB95.2 (2021)	15.9%	50.7%	21.8%	9.1%	2.4%

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 63.1 (2005) & 95.2 (2021)

3.6 Spain

In Spain, a biennial survey maps public opinion towards science since 2002 (Encuesta de Percepción Social de la Ciencia). Another one, specifically on the topic of disinformation in the scientific context, has been carried out in 2022 (Desinformación científica en España). Both are organised by the FECYT (Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología). In addition to these sources, results of a survey investigating attitudes towards science in the business sector in 2016 are available for Spain (Encuesta – Cultura Científica, Percepción y Actitudes ante la Ciencia y la Innovación en el Sector Empresarial Español) (detailed references for all surveys can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions provide more insights on what people in Spain think about trust in science generally and in the context of COVID-19, about research integrity and public integration in the research process.

3.6.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 34 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in Spain from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes towards science and also interest in scientific discoveries and the knowledge index have been lower in Spain than in other European countries in the 1990s. Since then, the picture has changed quite a bit: interest in and knowledge of science as well as the approval of the statement “Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable” haven risen beyond European average. In European comparison, many people in Spain are, however, convinced that science makes our lives change too fast.

Figure 34: Attitudes to science in Spain

att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
 att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
 att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
 sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
 k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.6.2 Trust in science

This section on trust in science presents two questions, both asked in the FECYT surveys of 2020 and 2022, one concerning the perceived benefits of science and one on science as the desired basis for developing laws and regulations in Spain. Additionally, the SCe project survey provides an insight into attitudes towards science in the Spanish business sector. Figures 35 and 36 show that the overall image of science in Spain has improved between 2020 and 2022. In 2022, considerably more respondents than in 2020 state that the benefits of science and technology outweigh their harms. Nearly three out of four respondents further agree in 2022 that scientific knowledge is the best basis for developing laws and regulations. On the other hand, in 2022, slightly more people thought that there are more harms than benefits of science and technology.

Figure 35: Benefit of science in Spain

Source: FECYT 2020 & 2022, own visualisation

Figure 36: Opinion on science as basis for decision-making in Spain

Source: FECYT 2020 & 2022, own visualisation

In Table 17, data from the SCe project indicates that the Spanish business sector overall does not associate science with mistrust. 35% of respondents answer that mistrust does not at all come to their minds when thinking about science and 24% say “a little”. 5.4% of respondents feel a lot of mistrust towards science.

Table 17: Mistrust in science in the Spanish business sector

Q.6.10. When you think of 'science' to what extent do these ideas come to mind?		
Mistrust	Not at all	35,4%
	A little	24,2%
	To an average extent	25,5%
	Quite a lot	8,9%
	A lot	5,4%
	Don't know	0,7%

Source: SCe Project 2020

Table 18 adds to this that a large majority of respondents from the Spanish business sector wishes for a more important role of scientists in business.

Table 18: Role of science in the Spanish business sector

Q11.1: Scientists should play a more important role in business		
	Don't agree	0,6%
	Slightly agree	1,8%
	Somewhat agree	17,3%
	Strongly agree	34,4%
	Fully agree	45,5%
	Don't know /NA	0,4%

Source: SCe Project 2020

3.6.3 COVID-19

The FECYT survey 2020 also included a question on measures for exiting the coronavirus pandemic. Table 19 shows the answers to it. Nearly half of the respondents consider the citizens' responsibility to be most important for ending the crisis, 30% rely on scientific discoveries for this.

Table 19: Perceived ways out of the coronavirus pandemic in Spain

P7. Of the following issues, please tell us the one you consider most important for the exit from the coronavirus crisis.		
	The citizens' responsibility	47,9%
	Scientific discoveries	30,1%
	Government management	21,1%
	Don't know	0,6%
	NA	0,3%

Source: FECYT 2020

3.6.4 Research integrity

Figure 37, based on data from the FECYT surveys in 2020 and 2022 and related to the concept of research integrity, shows that an increasing majority of respondents in Spain thinks that the financial funders of research can “influence scientists to reach conclusions that suit them”.

Figure 37: Perceived independence of scientists in Spain

Source: FECYT 2020 & 2022, own visualisation

3.6.5 Public integration

The last two items presented here relate to the concept of public integration in the scientific process, both coming from the FECYT survey 2020. Table 20 shows that the desired public integration in scientific decision-making is high in Spain: nearly 58% of respondents agree that citizens should have a greater role in this process when decisions directly affect them.

Table 20: Desired public integration in scientific decision-making in Spain

P21.D Citizens should have a greater role in decisions on science and technology that directly affect them.	Agree	57,8%
	Neither nor	16,0%
	Disagree	21,5%
	Don't know	4,2%
	NA	0,5%

Source: FECYT 2020

At the same time, Figure 38 indicates that respondents are not very much interested in getting involved in scientific decision-making themselves (personal integration).

Figure 38: Desired personal integration in scientific decision-making in Spain

Source: FECYT 2020, own visualisation

3.7 United Kingdom

In the UK, questions relevant to our research interest have been identified in several surveys carried out by Ipsos, some of them with a timeline dating back to the 1980s. More precisely, the here presented items come from the Ipsos Veracity Index 2022, from a survey on the topic “How has COVID-19 affected trust in scientists?” carried out in 2020 (Ipsos MORI), and from the Ipsos MORI Issues Index 2022 (detailed references for all surveys can be found in the References chapter at the end of the document). After the presentation of the timelines for the attitude items coming from the core item set defined in chapter 2, the other selected questions provide more insights about what people in the UK think about trust in science in general and in the particular context of the coronavirus pandemic. Finally, the evolution of environmental concerns as the most important issue in the UK over time is presented.

3.7.1 Attitudes to science

Figure 39 shows the evolution of attitudes to science in the UK from 1989 to 2021. The data on which these timelines are based is drawn from Eurobarometer surveys. The caption of the figure lists once again the actual wording of the items and their short name displayed in the figure (see also section 2.1.6). The figure shows that attitudes to science were settled closely to the European average (M=500) in the UK in the 1990s. Since then, all items have risen above European average, particularly the knowledge index but also rejection of the statements “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith” and “Science and technology make our lives change too fast”.

Figure 39: Attitudes to science in the United Kingdom

att1 health - *Science and technology make our lives healthier, easier and more comfortable (agree).*
 att3 too fast - *Science and technology make our lives change too fast (disagree).*
 att2 faith - *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith (disagree).*
 sci interest - *How interested are you in new scientific discoveries?*
 k13 - *knowledge index (various knowledge quiz items (true/false))*

Source: Eurobarometer surveys 1989-2021 (see Table 2)

3.7.2 Trust in science

The items presented in this section relate to British trust in science. Figure 40 demonstrates the evolution of trust in different professions since 1997 and highlights the role of scientists in it (Ipsos Veracity Index). Medical doctors continue to lead the public level of trust, but there might be a negative impact the coronavirus has had in this regard. While the overall level of trust in 16 professions and also in the “common men and women” remains stable over time, trust in scientists is on the increase since the 1990s (red line).

Figure 40: Trust in scientists in the United Kingdom over time

Source: Ipsos Veracity Index, own visualisation

Figure 41 shows answers to the question whether science provides benefits or has harmful effects for the UK (Ipsos MORI 2020). Most respondents are convinced of the positive effects science has for the country. Nevertheless, more than 1 out of 10 respondents has no answer to this question.

Figure 41: Benefit of science in the United Kingdom

Base: 11,646 online UK adults aged 16+ interviewed from 10 April to 17 August 2020

Source: Ipsos MORI 2020

3.7.3 COVID-19

The survey “How has COVID-19 affected trust in scientists?” includes many questions on trust in science in the particular context of the coronavirus pandemic and presents timelines of the evolution of public opinion between April and August 2020. Figure 42 shows that that people’s general attitude towards science apparently influences their feeling of trust (see also Wintterlin et al. 2022 and chapter 4): respondents who think that science is beneficial for society rate scientists as trustworthy much more often than those who do not think that science is beneficial.

Figure 42: Evolution of trust in scientists generally based on people’s existing dispositions towards science during the first months of the coronavirus pandemic in the United Kingdom

Source: Ipsos MORI 2020

Figure 43 then indicates that people’s perception of trustworthiness is slightly higher for scientists in general than for scientists advising the UK government on actions to deal with COVID-19.

Figure 43: Trustworthiness of scientists in times of COVID-19 in the United Kingdom

Base: 11,646 online UK adults aged 16+ interviewed from 10 April to 17 August 2020

Source: Ipsos MORI 2020

3.7.4 Climate change

The second topical focus of the POIESIS project is climate change. Figure 44, retrieved from the Ipsos MORI Issues Index report 2022, shows that the public perception of environmental concerns and climate change being the most important issue in the UK has evolved considerably since the 1990s, often influenced by major weather-related events. At the occasion of the COP26 in autumn 2021, 40% of respondents indicated that climate change was the most important issue for the UK today – the highest score recorded since 1988.

Figure 44: Evolution of environmental concerns as the most important issue in the United Kingdom

Pollution / Environment / Climate change

What do you see as the most/other important issues facing Britain today?

Base: representative sample of c.1,000 British adults age 18+ each month, interviewed face-to-face in home
 N.B. April 2020 data onwards is collected by telephone; previous months are face-to-face

Source: Ipsos MORI Issues Index

Source: Ipsos MORI Issues Index 2022

4 Empirical evidence on the relation of trust, integrity, and integration

Chapters 2 and 3 of this deliverable have shown that a number of surveys investigating public trust in science exist at the national and the multi-/international level and another small number of surveys already observed people's perspective on research integrity and public participation in the scientific process. Scientific evidence on the interrelation between these three concepts – trust, integrity and integration – is, however, rather scarce. It is exactly this interrelation POIESIS is interested in. Therefore, it is crucial to obtain an overview of the most important empirical findings that already exist in this regard. To this aim, a literature review has been conducted using the snowball system with the prominent survey experiment of Anvari and Lakens (2018) on research integrity as a starting point. This chapter presents the results of this research. The results presented here should however not be perceived as an exhaustive list of existing studies on the subject, but rather as a representation of the current state of the art and research's most important findings related to the topics at hand.

The chapter starts with a presentation of existing studies on research and scientists' integrity, more concretely covering the topics of support for controversial (medical) research as well as the so-called replication crisis and its consequences for citizens' perceptions of scientists' trustworthiness. In this context, the increasing use of open science practices and its potential to 'repair' damage caused by the replication crisis are discussed. Second, the chapter introduces different forms of public participation in the scientific process and presents the few studies analysing the interrelation of such participation with people's trust in science.

4.1 Research integrity

That scientists behave according to standards of research integrity should be the norm. It is therefore not surprising that studies find a large consensus among the public that behavioural practices such as data fraud as well as selective reporting in science are completely unacceptable and require severe punishments (Pickett and Roche 2018). Research integrity is however much more multi-faceted than such obviously 'wrong' behaviour.

Literature on research and scientists' integrity mostly relates to two topics that have been discussed publicly in the last decade: controversial research (such as stem cell research) and its public support, and the so-called 'replication crisis' and its consequences for the public perception of scientific studies. In both literatures, we can distinguish between people's perception of research integrity in relation to scientists' personal characteristics and in relation to external or circumstantial conditions such as the nature of the study's funding institution.

4.1.1 Support for controversial research

Trust in medical research has direct consequences for people's willingness to believe and participate in it. For instance, research has shown that "trust in politics and science increases the probability that people will accept and implement protective measures" in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (Dohle et al. 2020: 19, see also Tram et al. 2022). In the same vein, studies find that higher trust in biobanks comes with an increased willingness to donate and therefore to support medical research (Critchley et al. 2015; Dive et al. 2020). Milne et al. (2021) find transparency to be a crucial factor in this regard, meaning that citizens appreciate to know who will benefit from access to their data (in this case genomic data) and who is using it to which purpose (see also Aitken et al. 2016 and their focus group approach in Scotland). At the same time, Milne et al.'s large international survey across 22 countries hints at the importance of locally sensitive measures in order to increase trust in science

because there are large cross-country differences in the way citizens judge the trustworthiness of the collection and sharing of genomic data (Milne et al. 2021).

Three additional Australian studies with experimental design and sample sizes between 750 and 1700 participants, conducted between 2004 and 2018, shed more light on the variables influencing trust and support for controversial medical research, or more concretely stem cell research, in the public's view (Critchley 2008; Critchley et al. 2015; Dive et al. 2020). The most important variable in this regard appears to be who finances the biobanks, e.g. whether they are publicly or privately funded. All studies find the same public doubts about the integrity of privately funded research institutions compared to public ones. People trust these former institutions less and are less willing to donate to privately funded biobanks. The same applies to the question as to what kind of actors will gain access to the collected data (less trust when private actors are involved). People do not think that scientists in privately funded stem cell research institutions are less competent than their colleagues from a public research context, though. They precisely think that the benevolence of scientists is higher and that positive research results will be more accessible to the public when coming from publicly funded institutions (Critchley 2008). Similar tendencies can also be observed for the sharing of genetic data in an international context – with people being more reluctant to trust biobanks from other countries than from Australia – but the results are less conclusive than for the public – private dichotomy. Altogether, these studies show that citizens have important doubts about the research integrity of privately funded research institutions – a result presented here in the context of research on genetic data in Australia but confirmed at a more general level (trust in scientists in public vs. private institutions) also in representative surveys in the UK and the US (Krause et al. 2019) as well as in a study combining survey and experimental survey data (N = 504 and 588 respectively) in Germany (Rosman et al. 2022). It is not the research results' lower quality in private institutions that people fear, but a difference in the scientists' intrinsic motivation with them working rather towards commercial interests and financial profit than towards the public good.

4.1.2 The replication crisis

The second context in which the question of research and researchers' integrity has been widely discussed in recent years is the so-called 'replication crisis'. It questions the validity and credibility of scientific findings due to a series of failed replication attempts of previously performed scientific studies. This first became an issue in the field of psychological and medical science in the early 2000s, but since then similar questions have been asked in other disciplines as well (for an overview see Mede et al. 2021 and for psychology in particular Wingen 2022). In how far the replication crisis has reached the perception of citizens outside academia is still unclear – Mede et al. (2021) show for example that most Germans are unaware of it – but research has suggested that as soon as people learn about failed replication attempts of scientific studies, it has direct consequences on their perception of science and scientists.

From a macro perspective, the majority of studies dealing with this topic show that learning about the replication crisis and failed replication attempts reduces people's trust in (past) research (see Anvari and Lakens 2018, Hendriks et al. 2020 and Wingen et al. 2020 for online experimental surveys with citizens and Chopik et al. 2018 for an experiment among undergraduate students in the US (N=194)). Receiving the explanation that questionable research practices (QRPs) used in the initial studies are the reason for the failed replication attempts (in comparison to an explanation based on hidden moderators) further decreases people's trust in science. Successful replications, on the other hand, have a positive effect on people's view of science (Hendriks et al. 2020; Wingen et al. 2020). Several experimental studies therefore consistently find that failed replication attempts have negative consequences for citizens' perception of research.

Another picture is painted by a study presented by Mede et al. (2021). It is based on a nationally representative survey in Germany and shows that in this setting, views on the crisis are rather positive in the way that people underline replication attempt's function as quality assurance in research, and the fact that errors and corrections are a normal part of science. The discrepancy in the results comparing this survey and the above presented

studies might partly be explained by their different designs: while the survey in Mede et al.'s study (ibid) provided participants with very general information about recently failed attempts to replicate a certain number of scientific studies in different disciplines, the other experimental studies were more concrete and might therefore have generated more negative reactions among the participants. Wingen et al. (2020) find for example very concretely that participants provided with information about a particularly low replicability rate indicate significantly lower trust in psychology than participants who heard that a majority of studies could be successfully replicated.

Replication attempts of scientific studies may however not only have consequences for people's general view of science but also for their perception of the trustworthiness of individual scientists concerned by the failed replication. The literature finds that lay people generally base their trustworthiness judgements on three dimensions: perceived expertise, integrity, and benevolence (based on Hendriks et al. 2015). It is therefore directly relevant for the present report on empirical evidence concerning the relation between people's trust in science and research integrity. However, studies are inconclusive to what extent failed replication attempts and also scientists' own wrongness admission have negative (or even positive) consequences for the scientists' reputation.

Fetterman and Sassenberg (2015) show for instance that scientists generally fear but also over-estimate the negative reputational effects of failed replication efforts. Even more, their study demonstrates that admitting own mistakes in past research has a positive effect on one's reputation. In line with this finding, Hendriks et al. (2016) show that citizens indeed rate a scientist's integrity and benevolence higher when admitting flaws in previous research (compared to when it is exposed by others). The perception of scientists' expertise nevertheless suffers from flaws in their scientific studies, no matter by whom they are exposed. The same scientists, however, arrived at different results in a later study (Hendriks et al. 2020): in an experimental online survey, they find that people's judgement of scientists' trustworthiness is directly impacted by the success (or failure) of replication attempts. Further, and in contrast to their former results, in this study, scientists' self-admission of the failure does not have positive consequences for people's perception of scientists' integrity and benevolence.

Finally, Altenmüller et al. (2021) also find that expressing self-criticism has no negative consequences on people's perception of the scientists' trustworthiness. Even more, explicitly not being self-corrective (in direct comparison to scientists who are) has negative consequences for the scientists' trustworthiness, their credibility and people's willingness to engage with them further. It has to be noted, though, that the framing of this study was profoundly different from the others presented here. Participants of this study read interviews, in which scientists either admitted that they might maybe have committed research mistakes in the past (without being sure of it) or stated that there was no possibility they might have made such mistakes. Participants were however not exposed to an actual reporting of replication failures of the scientists' research. This likely has consequences for the participants' interpretation of the situation and the scientists' trustworthiness.

Altogether, one can conclude that the replication crisis and people being informed about failed replication attempts of scientific studies might have negative consequences for people's trust in science and partly also their perception of individual scientists' trustworthiness. What becomes very clear, though, is that all these studies' findings seem highly contextual and that there are many confounding factors at play which require more and detailed research.

From a different point of view, the question also needs to be raised whether the academic and public discussion should actually focus on failed replication attempts of former studies or whether it is rather the reproducibility of scientific studies that needs to be improved. Many research findings cannot be replicated due to the unique nature of their setting, participants etc. The crucial aspect for the academic community is however, whether they are published with enough transparency and providing enough details about the research process and the studies' implementation that they can be reproduced by peers in another context or at another point in time. This objective – boosting transparency in the scientific process – is the core of what has become known as the 'open science movement' in academia in recent years.

4.1.3 Open Science as remedy for lost trust?

One of the potential solutions presented to solve the ‘replication crisis’ and to restore public trust in science is the open science movement (Wingen 2022). Central aspects of it are the transparent publishing of materials, data and codes, the preregistration of studies, the call for more collaboration and the area-wide implementation of Transparency and Openness Promotion Guidelines (Dienlin et al. 2020). Its main objective is to make science more transparent and accessible to everyone. In this regard, it partly relates to the next section of this chapter, namely the influence of societal integration in the research process on people’s trust in science. As such, the open science movement is still a rather science-internal affair, though, with scientists being judged by laypeople from the outside.

Once again, empirical evidence on whether open science practices may increase people’s trust in science and whether they might be able to repair damage caused by the replication crisis is rather inconclusive. While survey data indicates that people claim to trust scientific studies more when the corresponding data is openly available (Pew Research Center 2019; Rosman et al. 2022), scientists raise the argument that such self-reporting in surveys might be biased, for example by social desirability (Rosman et al. 2022). Among the available survey experiments on the topic, then, there is mixed evidence on potential positive effects of the use of open science methods: Schneider et al. (2019) show in their research that badges in the beginning of an article indicating that the study has been conducted under open science standards increase trust in it among fellow scientists and undergraduate students. Citizens, however, only react to badges indicating explicitly that a study is not compliant with the principles of open science – such information decreases their trust in the study. Altenmüller et al. (2021) find that even minor open science reform intentions formulated by scientists have a large positive effect on people’s perception of their trustworthiness and credibility. As a reminder, in their study, participants read interviews with fictional scientists talking about their past and future work. As part of the interview, they were asked whether they would implement open science reforms in their future studies or not.

Other studies directly exposed participants to information about failed replication efforts of scientific studies and then explained potential remedies, such as an extended use of open science methods. These studies could not find any ‘repair effect’ of open science practices buffering the negative impact learning about the replication crisis had for people’s trust in science (Anvari and Lakens 2018; Wingen et al. 2020). Even on the contrary, Anvari and Lakens (2018) find that people who are informed about open science reforms that might improve replication efforts in the future significantly trust less in future research than people who do not receive this information. Next to a methodological explanation, they also raise the argument that laypeople learning about the fact that transparency should be a crucial part of future research might actually be shocked that this is not yet the case. This could explain their decrease of trust in future research. A similar reason might also explain why laypeople only reacted (negatively) to a non-compliance open science badge in the study of Schneider et al. (2019) but not positively to the one that indicated the study’s compliance with open science standards. Wingen et al. (2022) hint to a potential risk of increasingly used open science practices by demonstrating that without further explanation, citizens do not make a difference between preprints and peer-reviewed publications. Therefore, they might consider the former as valid scientific information. The authors are however also able to show that with only a short explanatory note, people are successfully able to judge on the state of the research presented in the article.

Empirical evidence on the influence of open science practices on people’s trust in science is hitherto rather mixed. It seems that open science practices are generally perceived positively by the public but that they cannot entirely make up for the negative impact the replication crisis might have on scientists’ trustworthiness and credibility. It is further unclear whether scientists’ self-admission of flaws in their past research actually has positive or negative reputational consequences.

4.2 Societal integration in the research process

Besides research integrity, another topic has been widely discussed in relation to public trust in science in recent years: the increasing integration of citizens in different phases of the research cycle. Such public engagement in science can appear in many different forms and shapes. For example, and as already mentioned, open science practices aiming to make science more transparent and accessible to the public already partly fit this idea. The public's participation in open science remains, however, rather passive in that citizens are able to better inform themselves, but do not as such contribute to the research results. Fundamentally, science communication describes the way scientific findings and methods are communicated to laypeople. It aims to involve the public more strongly in the area of scientific research by improving the ways in which research results are presented to and especially discussed with the public (e.g. Nerghes et al. 2022; Wintterlin et al. 2022). Probably the most active and direct public involvement in the scientific research process can be found in what is mostly called citizen science. Citizen science very broadly refers to the participation of non-scientists in scientific projects. This can take the form of citizens collecting data, designing experiments, participating in round tables, etc.

It has been proven difficult to define these different concepts distinctively. They clearly interact with one another, and it is a still ongoing debate which activities of public engagement should be 'assigned' to which concept (see for instance Haklay et al. 2021 for the difficulties to find a universally applicable definition of citizen science). Further, there are even more forms of public engagement in science that are not necessarily covered by open science, science communication or citizen science projects (e.g. public consultations). Societal integration in science therefore is a large field and it is a constantly changing one. The last two decades have seen the interaction of science and the public changing "from public understanding to public engagement" (Schäfer 2009: 475). One declared objective of this increased public integration in the scientific process in all its various forms is to foster public trust in science (Bedessem et al. 2021; Wintterlin et al. 2022). However, almost no empirical evidence exists on the effectiveness of this approach. The remainder of this chapter presents a few relevant scientific findings in this regard, highlighting the evidence gaps on the interrelation between societal integration in the research process and public trust in science.

From a rather broad perspective, Wintterlin et al. (2022), in a nationally representative survey on potential predictors for trust in science in Switzerland, find that the frequency of citizens' experiences with science is not one of them. This means that how often people are in contact with science or scientific information – online or offline, through media or in person – does not significantly influence how much they trust in science. This seems plausible as the quality and kind of public interaction with science might be more important than its frequency. Their survey shows that positivistic attitudes towards science, meaning "optimistic views on science and its merits for individuals and society" (ibid: 6), best predict people's level of trust in science.

Several studies on public engagement in science, be it in the form of science communication or others, show that generally, support for increased societal integration in the research process is strong as much among citizens as among scientists and experts. At the same time, important divergences have been found, for example in the medialisation of different scientific disciplines in German print media (Schäfer 2009), in the idea of what successful science communication could and should look like – with a focus on a rather traditional one-way process of information transmission – among scientists in the Netherlands (Nerghes et al. 2022), and in the perception of whether laypeople actually may or may not be capable of participating in particularly complex scientific processes, precisely in regulatory science in Germany (Dendler and Böhl 2021).

The term citizen science first appeared in the 1990s, but theory and practice of the concept have gained considerable importance in the last decade (Vohland et al. 2021b). Entire citizen science networks have developed in many countries and institutional funding for citizen science projects has increased (ibid). There already is abundant literature on the concept of citizen science, its methods and practice (see for example the peer-reviewed journal *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* (<https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/>) as well as the already cited book *The Science of Citizen Science* (Vohland et al. 2021a)). However, empirical work often remains restricted to small case studies (for an overview see Lorke and Schmid-Loertzer 2022). This might be because the impact of citizen science

projects can best be evaluated in the context of concrete projects, but the generalisability of the findings is obviously problematic.

Even though several such case studies exist, the topic of trust in science does not usually seem to be in their focus of interest. Vitone et al. (2016) find that undergraduate students in Florida do not rate their own trust in science higher after their participation in a citizen science project than they did before. Apart from this, one other study could be identified that deals precisely with the question whether participation in citizen science projects increases public trust in science: Bedessem et al. (2021) performed an online citizen science quasi-experiment situated in the discipline of urban studies. More concretely, they carried out a two-phase quasi-experiment concerning the delineation of metropolitan areas of Poland's two major cities. In phase 1, they recruited 174 citizens living in Region A via social media. Those citizens participated in a citizen science project aimed at delineating their metropolitan area. Then, in phase 2, 164 participants from Region A and 158 participants from Region B have once again been recruited via social media and answered questions about the metropolitan maps of their respective regions. Specifically, participants received the respective map and additional information about how it had been created: with the help of a citizen science project in Region A and by traditional academic means in Region B (using historical data and econometric regression methods). Participants from both regions were then asked to what extent the resulting map is a good representation of the area and to what extent it can be trusted. The analysis shows that people from Region A, in which the map had been created with the help of a citizen science project, trusted the result significantly more often than people from Region B. A more fine-grained analysis then demonstrates that these differences stem mostly from people with primary and secondary education: they trust the result from the citizen science project more than the one based on traditional academic research methods. For people with university education no such difference could be identified at a statistically significant level. Important to note is that around 80% of the participants in the survey (phase 2) of Region A had not previously participated in phase 1. This means that citizen science projects may increase trust in research results among the general public and not only among the participants of the projects themselves. The study participants did in fact not show higher levels of trust than the non-participants. This study sheds a positive light on the influence citizen science projects might have on public trust in concrete research results. The authors however also hint at potential difficulties concerning the generalisability of their findings: first of all, their surveys in phase 2 are based on non-representative samples of the regions' inhabitants which might have led to biases in the results; and secondly, local and cultural variables might be at play, making it difficult to make statements about the 'general public' in this regard. Additionally, one should not confound the here studied trust in concrete research results and people's more general trust in science. Differences between both may very well also exist in relation to citizen science.

Nevertheless, the overall result of this study with a focus on the influence that increased societal integration in the research process might have on public trust in science is rather positive. More research is needed, however, in order to be able to generalise its results.

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter has presented the current state of empirical evidence on the question whether and how research integrity and increased societal integration in the research process may impact public trust in science, research and innovation.

Studies on research integrity have been shown to exist mostly in relation to support for controversial research and in the context of the so-called replication crisis. People are generally more doubtful about the trustworthiness of scientists working in privately funded research institutions than in public ones – a consistent finding throughout all forms of empirical research, be it representative surveys or studies with experimental design. With regard to the 'replication crisis' and potential ways to restore public trust in science in its context, research findings are much less conclusive. It seems that citizens mostly react negatively to information about the replication crisis. More concretely, learning about failed replication efforts of scientific studies might

negatively influence citizens' trust in science and their perception of individual scientists' trustworthiness. Scientists' self-admission of flaws in their past research, then, might eventually have a positive influence on their reputation, but evidence is inconclusive. Similarly, the impact of adherence to open science practices on trust among citizens, and its capability to repair damage done by information about the replication crisis, are yet unknown.

Altogether, scientific findings on the replication crisis and the use of open science practices have actually proven to be highly contextual. For example, there seem to be divergences in the research results on the topic when comparing questions from surveys building on respondents' former knowledge or providing rather general information on the topic, and experimental surveys in which participants react to very concrete information, for example on the scope of the replication crisis. In the former setting, citizens appear to be less critical and evaluate research integrity from a more benevolent perspective than in the latter. There might be differences across national and cultural contexts, as well. Basically, many confounding factors are at play in the relation between research integrity and public trust in science that have not been examined in detail, yet.

We were able to identify only few empirical studies on the influence of societal integration in the research process on people's trust in science. The field of public engagement in science in its various forms has grown considerably in the last decade. There seems to be a discrepancy between the general will to increase such engagement among citizens and experts and knowledge about the consequences thereof. Concerning trust in science more precisely, apart from a few theoretical contributions, only one empirical study could be found putting its main focus on the matter. The study from Poland deals with the question whether citizen science projects may foster citizens' trust in research results. It presents positive results in this regard but also underlines the need for more research in order to generalise statements on the question whether public engagement in the scientific process can influence people's trust in science.

In sum, this literature review clearly demonstrates the need for a stronger empirical focus on questions related to research integrity, societal engagement in the research process, and their impact on societal trust in science. It is generally assumed that a lack of scientific transparency and reproducibility of scientific findings on the one hand and lacking public integration in the scientific process on the other hand lead directly to public mistrust in science. A literature review of empirical evidence on these questions, however, shows that there are many breaks in that line that we are not yet able to explain. These breaks are exactly what POIESIS will be analysing in the upcoming years: it is our objective to identify and examine confounding variables as well as mediating actors in this relationship. In doing so, POIESIS aims to disentangle the interplay of research integrity, public integration in the scientific process and trust in science and to provide well-founded input for how to improve it.

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6 Appendix A – Core items results

QA12a.10 (EB 95.2; 2021)				
The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly: Know best what is good for people.				
Rank-ordered on 'Describes well'				
	Describes well	Describes badly	Don't know	Total
TR - Turkey	78.8%	20.0%	1.2%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	76.3%	14.2%	9.5%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	70.8%	20.6%	8.7%	100.0%
GR - Greece	67.8%	26.6%	5.6%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	67.8%	9.7%	22.5%	100.0%
ES - Spain	67.6%	18.0%	14.3%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	63.3%	36.6%	0.1%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	62.4%	25.3%	12.4%	100.0%
IT - Italy	61.4%	32.5%	6.1%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	57.4%	29.6%	12.9%	100.0%
MT - Malta	57.1%	19.2%	23.6%	100.0%
RO - Romania	55.0%	31.9%	13.0%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	53.9%	45.5%	0.6%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	52.6%	34.5%	12.9%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	52.6%	26.6%	20.8%	100.0%
PL - Poland	52.1%	26.7%	21.2%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	51.2%	48.5%	0.3%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	50.8%	48.7%	0.5%	100.0%
NO - Norway	50.5%	48.6%	0.9%	100.0%
EU+ average	49.9%	40.7%	9.4%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	48.2%	35.1%	16.7%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	47.4%	32.6%	20.0%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	47.3%	52.2%	0.5%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	46.9%	48.6%	4.4%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	46.3%	46.8%	6.8%	100.0%
AL - Albania	46.0%	27.0%	27.0%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	44.9%	36.3%	18.8%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	43.2%	56.1%	0.7%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	42.5%	56.7%	0.8%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	41.8%	57.2%	1.0%	100.0%
FI - Finland	41.0%	57.9%	1.2%	100.0%
AT - Austria	41.0%	43.9%	15.1%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	37.7%	38.4%	23.8%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	37.7%	61.9%	0.4%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	37.5%	54.6%	7.9%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	35.2%	64.0%	0.8%	100.0%
FR - France	33.6%	52.6%	13.8%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	28.9%	61.3%	9.8%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	26.7%	72.0%	1.3%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	25.7%	53.6%	20.7%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	25.2%	54.1%	20.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	37.5%	39.5%	23.1%	100.0%
Germany weighted	27.6%	51.2%	21.2%	100.0%

QA17.8 (EB 95.2; 2021)

How strongly do you agree or disagree with the following statements? We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.

Rank-ordered on 'Agree'

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree - disagree	Don't know	Total
HU - Hungary	28.8%	38.7%	33.8%	21.6%	7.7%	2.7%	5.2%	28.6%	0.6%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	23.7%	42.1%	32.9%	19.0%	6.9%	2.3%	4.6%	28.3%	6.0%	100.0%
PL - Poland	18.8%	46.8%	32.8%	21.2%	10.4%	1.9%	6.2%	26.7%	1.0%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	34.0%	30.6%	32.3%	17.2%	10.9%	5.9%	8.4%	23.9%	1.4%	100.0%
IT - Italy	13.7%	50.2%	32.0%	22.9%	7.9%	4.1%	6.0%	26.0%	1.2%	100.0%
ES - Spain	31.1%	30.8%	31.0%	12.7%	14.1%	8.5%	11.3%	19.7%	2.8%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	15.7%	42.9%	29.3%	26.3%	9.6%	3.1%	6.4%	23.0%	2.4%	100.0%
GR - Greece	15.0%	43.2%	29.1%	26.7%	10.9%	3.0%	7.0%	22.2%	1.1%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	26.0%	32.0%	29.0%	23.9%	10.7%	2.8%	6.8%	22.3%	4.6%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	14.4%	43.0%	28.7%	28.8%	9.2%	3.3%	6.3%	22.5%	1.3%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	25.0%	31.6%	28.3%	23.6%	8.1%	6.9%	7.5%	20.8%	4.7%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	17.1%	39.3%	28.2%	28.4%	11.1%	2.8%	7.0%	21.3%	1.4%	100.0%
MT - Malta	15.0%	41.3%	28.2%	23.2%	12.2%	1.7%	7.0%	21.2%	6.5%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	15.6%	39.4%	27.5%	28.9%	10.2%	5.8%	8.0%	19.5%	0.1%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	18.8%	35.1%	27.0%	25.0%	13.0%	7.4%	10.2%	16.8%	0.7%	100.0%
AT - Austria	15.1%	37.9%	26.5%	20.1%	17.2%	8.1%	12.7%	13.9%	1.6%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	17.0%	35.4%	26.2%	27.3%	10.3%	4.6%	7.5%	18.8%	5.4%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	8.6%	42.7%	25.7%	23.6%	20.2%	4.9%	12.6%	13.1%		100.0%
FR - France	15.5%	35.4%	25.5%	16.8%	18.9%	10.6%	14.8%	10.7%	2.8%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	7.5%	43.1%	25.3%	23.2%	22.3%	4.0%	13.2%	12.2%		100.0%
LT - Lithuania	11.8%	37.9%	24.9%	32.4%	13.6%	4.2%	8.9%	16.0%	0.1%	100.0%
EU+ average	13.4%	36.1%	24.8%	25.7%	17.1%	6.3%	11.7%	13.1%	1.4%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	19.3%	30.1%	24.7%	27.3%	14.2%	9.0%	11.6%	13.1%	0.1%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	19.2%	30.0%	24.6%	20.1%	15.7%	12.4%	14.1%	10.6%	2.6%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	8.4%	40.3%	24.4%	31.8%	14.7%	4.8%	9.8%	14.6%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	8.1%	38.7%	23.4%	22.5%	23.1%	7.7%	15.4%	8.0%		100.0%
EE - Estonia	5.3%	40.8%	23.1%	26.4%	22.2%	5.3%	13.8%	9.3%		100.0%
BE - Belgium	6.3%	39.7%	23.0%	26.6%	22.4%	4.9%	13.7%	9.4%		100.0%
RO - Romania	13.6%	31.9%	22.8%	30.6%	15.0%	5.6%	10.3%	12.5%	3.2%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	8.1%	33.1%	20.6%	22.9%	27.2%	8.4%	17.8%	2.8%	0.4%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	4.2%	36.8%	20.5%	22.4%	30.0%	6.6%	18.3%	2.2%		100.0%
FI - Finland	4.5%	35.7%	20.1%	29.9%	26.0%	3.9%	15.0%	5.2%		100.0%
IS - Iceland	5.4%	32.8%	19.1%	36.7%	19.7%	5.0%	12.4%	6.8%	0.4%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	7.0%	31.1%	19.1%	21.9%	32.3%	7.7%	20.0%	-1.0%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	7.9%	29.8%	18.9%	26.2%	23.7%	11.2%	17.5%	1.4%	1.2%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	10.0%	26.0%	18.0%	18.8%	25.6%	17.4%	21.5%	-3.5%	2.2%	100.0%
NO - Norway	4.2%	31.4%	17.8%	30.5%	25.6%	8.3%	17.0%	0.8%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	5.0%	29.4%	17.2%	24.8%	30.2%	10.6%	20.4%	-3.2%		100.0%
SE - Sweden	4.7%	26.3%	15.5%	31.3%	27.8%	10.0%	18.9%	-3.4%		100.0%
AL - Albania	4.6%	21.9%	13.3%	56.3%	9.3%	7.9%	8.6%	4.7%		100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	9.5%	25.1%	17.3%	19.0%	26.1%	18.1%	22.1%	-4.8%	2.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	22.0%	29.0%	25.5%	19.7%	15.0%	11.7%	13.4%	12.2%	2.7%	100.0%
Germany avg	12.0%	25.9%	19.0%	19.1%	23.9%	16.8%	20.4%	-1.4%	2.3%	100.0%

Q8.3 (EB 73.1; 2010)

To what extent do you agree with the following statements? We can no longer trust scientists to tell the truth about controversial scientific and technological issues because they depend more and more on money from industry

Rank-ordered on 'Agree'

	Totally agree	Tend to agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree - disagree	Don't know	Total
DE-E Germany East	37.1%	37.6%	37.4%	15.5%	6.8%	1.1%	4.0%	33.4%	1.9%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	44.8%	26.7%	35.8%	16.5%	3.8%	0.6%	2.2%	33.6%	7.6%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	37.2%	34.0%	35.6%	14.1%	8.2%	3.9%	6.1%	29.6%	2.7%	100.0%
FI - Finland	21.7%	49.4%	35.6%	14.5%	11.0%	1.0%	6.0%	29.6%	2.5%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	21.2%	47.5%	34.4%	13.1%	12.4%	4.1%	8.3%	26.1%	1.8%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	28.0%	40.5%	34.3%	21.2%	7.0%	0.9%	4.0%	30.3%	2.4%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	30.4%	37.6%	34.0%	19.4%	7.3%	2.4%	4.9%	29.2%	2.9%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	29.3%	38.0%	33.7%	18.5%	6.6%	2.4%	4.5%	29.2%	5.2%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	27.3%	39.1%	33.2%	13.5%	13.3%	2.8%	8.1%	25.2%	4.1%	100.0%
NO - Norway	20.3%	44.9%	32.6%	14.2%	13.6%	4.7%	9.2%	23.5%	2.3%	100.0%
FR - France	23.4%	41.7%	32.6%	14.2%	11.3%	3.9%	7.6%	25.0%	5.4%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	24.1%	40.8%	32.5%	18.7%	6.7%	1.4%	4.1%	28.4%	8.3%	100.0%
GR - Greece	21.7%	42.1%	31.9%	25.8%	7.1%	1.1%	4.1%	27.8%	2.2%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	21.7%	40.6%	31.2%	22.5%	9.3%	2.2%	5.8%	25.4%	3.8%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	16.5%	43.6%	30.1%	22.6%	12.4%	2.6%	7.5%	22.6%	2.4%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	19.3%	40.8%	30.1%	22.0%	12.2%	2.8%	7.5%	22.6%	3.0%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	18.7%	40.3%	29.5%	17.2%	18.1%	3.1%	10.6%	18.9%	2.7%	100.0%
EU+ average	21.2%	37.6%	29.4%	20.0%	11.8%	3.1%	7.5%	22.0%	6.3%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	22.5%	35.6%	29.1%	19.1%	11.8%	4.4%	8.1%	21.0%	6.7%	100.0%
ES - Spain	24.0%	33.9%	29.0%	15.6%	14.7%	4.6%	9.7%	19.3%	7.2%	100.0%
AT - Austria	17.1%	40.4%	28.8%	27.2%	9.6%	1.5%	5.6%	23.2%	4.2%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	16.6%	40.9%	28.8%	22.8%	17.6%	1.4%	9.5%	19.3%	0.8%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	23.6%	33.8%	28.7%	23.2%	12.7%	2.4%	7.6%	21.2%	4.3%	100.0%
IT - Italy	16.5%	38.1%	27.3%	25.5%	12.3%	3.5%	7.9%	19.4%	4.0%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	20.0%	34.6%	27.3%	19.9%	7.6%	1.9%	4.8%	22.6%	16.0%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	15.1%	38.3%	26.7%	27.8%	11.7%	3.5%	7.6%	19.1%	3.6%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	16.3%	34.9%	25.6%	20.0%	19.3%	5.6%	12.5%	13.2%	3.9%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	10.2%	40.8%	25.5%	23.3%	13.5%	1.9%	7.7%	17.8%	10.2%	100.0%
NI - Northern Ireland	15.2%	35.4%	25.3%	23.8%	14.9%	3.3%	9.1%	16.2%	7.3%	100.0%
RO - Romania	15.8%	34.0%	24.9%	21.1%	12.1%	3.3%	7.7%	17.2%	13.8%	100.0%
PL - Poland	14.8%	33.3%	24.1%	25.8%	13.2%	2.6%	7.9%	16.2%	10.3%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	25.8%	20.8%	23.3%	18.7%	8.7%	8.9%	8.8%	14.5%	17.0%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	12.2%	32.9%	22.6%	25.7%	20.4%	5.3%	12.9%	9.7%	3.5%	100.0%
MT - Malta	11.0%	30.4%	20.7%	14.6%	11.4%	5.6%	8.5%	12.2%	27.0%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	10.1%	27.0%	18.6%	21.1%	19.6%	3.4%	11.5%	7.1%	18.9%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	28.2%	40.0%	34.1%	20.6%	7.3%	1.5%	4.4%	29.7%	2.4%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	35.1%	38.4%	36.8%	15.6%	7.5%	0.9%	4.2%	32.6%	2.4%	100.0%
Germany weighted	29.7%	39.6%	34.7%	19.5%	7.3%	1.4%	4.4%	30.3%	2.4%	100.0%

QA11.1 (EB 95.2; 2021)

We can no longer trust scientists to tell the truth about controversial scientific and technological issues because they depend increasingly on money from industry

Rank-ordered by 'Agree'

	Totally agree	Tend to agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree - disagree	Don't know	Total
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	41.5%	30.8%	36.2%	15.8%	7.5%	3.2%	5.4%	30.8%	1.2%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	29.1%	31.6%	30.4%	23.0%	11.2%	3.4%	7.3%	23.1%	1.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	25.4%	32.9%	29.2%	22.7%	11.9%	3.8%	7.9%	21.3%	3.3%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	26.2%	32.1%	29.2%	29.9%	8.7%	3.2%	6.0%	23.2%		100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	24.3%	33.5%	28.9%	23.8%	6.8%	4.3%	5.6%	23.4%	7.2%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	20.6%	37.1%	28.9%	30.8%	8.2%	2.6%	5.4%	23.5%	0.7%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	18.2%	38.6%	28.4%	29.9%	10.7%	2.7%	6.7%	21.7%		100.0%
ES - Spain	23.3%	33.3%	28.3%	15.8%	16.1%	7.8%	12.0%	16.4%	3.7%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	17.2%	39.2%	28.2%	26.7%	8.1%	2.8%	5.5%	22.8%	6.1%	100.0%
FR - France	21.9%	33.4%	27.7%	21.9%	14.5%	5.4%	10.0%	17.7%	3.0%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	17.6%	37.4%	27.5%	30.3%	10.1%	2.9%	6.5%	21.0%	1.7%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	16.4%	38.6%	27.5%	29.9%	10.9%	3.2%	7.1%	20.5%	0.9%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	19.1%	35.6%	27.4%	22.8%	8.4%	2.7%	5.6%	21.8%	11.5%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	15.2%	39.3%	27.3%	30.1%	13.1%	2.3%	7.7%	19.6%		100.0%
AT - Austria	17.0%	37.4%	27.2%	24.3%	13.6%	3.9%	8.8%	18.5%	3.8%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	15.0%	39.4%	27.2%	22.7%	18.5%	4.4%	11.5%	15.8%		100.0%
ME - Montenegro	19.4%	33.3%	26.4%	28.4%	15.1%	3.0%	9.1%	17.3%	0.8%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	14.0%	38.1%	26.1%	24.4%	18.7%	4.6%	11.7%	14.4%	0.2%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	20.3%	30.4%	25.4%	27.8%	9.4%	4.2%	6.8%	18.6%	8.0%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	17.5%	33.0%	25.3%	23.9%	17.4%	5.0%	11.2%	14.1%	3.1%	100.0%
FI - Finland	8.5%	41.3%	24.9%	25.4%	20.0%	4.7%	12.4%	12.6%	0.1%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	9.3%	40.4%	24.9%	21.0%	23.3%	5.9%	14.6%	10.3%		100.0%
EU+ average	15.6%	33.9%	24.8%	28.0%	15.8%	4.5%	10.2%	14.6%	2.2%	100.0%
IT - Italy	11.8%	37.6%	24.7%	31.5%	14.0%	2.8%	8.4%	16.3%	2.4%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	9.7%	38.9%	24.3%	26.9%	21.0%	3.6%	12.3%	12.0%		100.0%
GR - Greece	14.0%	33.8%	23.9%	31.6%	17.3%	1.8%	9.6%	14.4%	1.4%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	13.2%	34.3%	23.8%	26.8%	18.9%	4.7%	11.8%	12.0%	2.0%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	17.4%	30.0%	23.7%	30.4%	12.8%	4.5%	8.7%	15.1%	4.9%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	10.8%	36.4%	23.6%	27.6%	18.5%	6.8%	12.7%	11.0%		100.0%
PL - Poland	13.7%	32.9%	23.3%	28.8%	16.7%	3.8%	10.3%	13.1%	4.2%	100.0%
NO - Norway	8.2%	36.2%	22.2%	31.0%	19.9%	4.7%	12.3%	9.9%		100.0%
RO - Romania	19.4%	24.7%	22.1%	36.0%	11.4%	4.3%	7.9%	14.2%	4.2%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	9.7%	34.2%	22.0%	25.6%	24.1%	6.3%	15.2%	6.8%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	9.4%	32.7%	21.1%	30.4%	19.1%	6.4%	12.8%	8.3%	2.0%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	8.3%	31.7%	20.0%	26.7%	26.8%	6.5%	16.7%	3.4%	0.1%	100.0%
MT - Malta	9.9%	27.8%	18.9%	28.2%	21.0%	4.4%	12.7%	6.2%	8.8%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	7.7%	28.6%	18.2%	28.9%	28.2%	6.6%	17.4%	0.8%		100.0%
IS - Iceland	4.1%	29.9%	17.0%	38.6%	22.8%	4.4%	13.6%	3.4%	0.2%	100.0%
AL - Albania	9.8%	19.3%	14.6%	54.1%	10.4%	6.3%	8.4%	6.2%	0.1%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	4.2%	21.1%	12.7%	32.7%	33.4%	8.6%	21.0%	-8.4%		100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	17.4%	32.7%	25.1%	23.3%	18.2%	5.1%	11.7%	13.4%	3.3%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	27.1%	31.8%	29.5%	23.7%	10.7%	3.3%	7.0%	22.5%	3.3%	100.0%
Germany weighted	19.3%	32.5%	25.9%	23.4%	16.7%	4.8%	10.8%	15.2%	3.3%	100.0%

QD17t (EB 79.2; 2013)

Do you think that the results of publicly funded research should be made available online free of charge? (Yes, to the general public / Yes, to other researchers / Yes, to industries / No / DK)

Rank-ordered by 'Total Yes'

	Not mentioned	Total 'Yes'	Total
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	9.5%	90.5%	100.0%
FI - Finland	9.7%	90.3%	100.0%
GR - Greece	11.6%	88.4%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	13.6%	86.4%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	14.4%	85.6%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	14.7%	85.3%	100.0%
GB-NIR Northern Ireland	15.3%	84.7%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	15.5%	84.5%	100.0%
GB-GBN - Great Britain	16.0%	84.0%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	16.2%	83.8%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	17.4%	82.6%	100.0%
IT - Italy	18.5%	81.5%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	18.8%	81.2%	100.0%
ES - Spain	19.3%	80.7%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	19.5%	80.5%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	19.7%	80.3%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	19.8%	80.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	20.3%	79.7%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	20.4%	79.6%	100.0%
FR - France	21.1%	78.9%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	21.4%	78.6%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	21.9%	78.1%	100.0%
PL - Poland	24.3%	75.7%	100.0%
AT - Austria	24.4%	75.6%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	25.8%	74.2%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	25.8%	74.2%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	27.2%	72.8%	100.0%
MT - Malta	27.4%	72.6%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	31.3%	68.7%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	34.0%	66.0%	100.0%
RO - Romania	34.2%	65.8%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	27.8%	72.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	30.3%	69.7%	100.0%
Germany weighted	28.4%	71.6%	100.0%

QA9.5 (EB 95.2; 2021)

The following are some statements that people have made about science or technology. For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree. The results of publicly funded research, such as scientific articles and data, should be made available online free of charge

Rank-ordered by 'Agree'

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree - disagree	Don't know	Total
PT - Portugal	66.9%	28.2%	47.6%	3.5%	1.0%	0.4%	0.7%	46.9%		100.0%
IE - Ireland	57.0%	36.6%	46.8%	5.2%	1.0%	0.2%	0.6%	46.2%		100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	55.5%	35.5%	45.5%	5.9%	2.7%	0.5%	1.6%	43.9%		100.0%
BE - Belgium	52.0%	38.7%	45.4%	7.6%	1.7%		1.7%	43.7%	0.1%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	54.4%	36.3%	45.4%	7.3%	2.0%	0.1%	1.1%	44.3%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	48.5%	41.5%	45.0%	7.5%	1.5%	1.0%	1.3%	43.8%		100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	47.5%	42.4%	45.0%	8.5%	1.3%	0.2%	0.8%	44.2%		100.0%
SE - Sweden	56.6%	31.3%	44.0%	10.8%	0.8%	0.6%	0.7%	43.3%		100.0%
TR - Turkey	56.2%	31.7%	44.0%	9.3%	1.9%	0.9%	1.4%	42.6%	0.1%	100.0%
NO - Norway	59.0%	28.9%	44.0%	10.8%	1.2%	0.1%	0.7%	43.3%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	46.1%	41.6%	43.9%	9.0%	3.0%	0.3%	1.7%	42.2%		100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	69.6%	18.0%	43.8%	6.5%	2.4%	1.6%	2.0%	41.8%	2.0%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	52.1%	35.3%	43.7%	9.1%	2.3%	0.9%	1.6%	42.1%	0.3%	100.0%
FI - Finland	47.8%	39.2%	43.5%	9.7%	2.7%	0.6%	1.7%	41.9%		100.0%
LV - Latvia	45.2%	38.8%	42.0%	13.2%	2.0%	0.8%	1.4%	40.6%		100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	52.3%	31.2%	41.8%	8.9%	3.5%	1.4%	2.5%	39.3%	2.7%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	48.1%	34.6%	41.4%	15.6%	1.5%	0.2%	0.9%	40.5%		100.0%
SI - Slovenia	48.6%	33.9%	41.3%	10.9%	3.4%	1.6%	2.5%	38.8%	1.7%	100.0%
MT - Malta	48.2%	34.1%	41.2%	9.9%	0.8%		0.8%	40.4%	7.0%	100.0%
GR - Greece	51.4%	30.3%	40.9%	13.6%	1.9%	0.3%	1.1%	39.8%	2.5%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	33.8%	46.4%	40.1%	15.6%	3.4%	0.9%	2.2%	38.0%		100.0%
FR - France	41.1%	38.3%	39.7%	10.3%	4.9%	2.7%	3.8%	35.9%	2.7%	100.0%
ES - Spain	50.2%	29.2%	39.7%	10.2%	4.1%	2.0%	3.1%	36.7%	4.4%	100.0%
EU+ average	43.4%	35.3%	39.4%	13.9%	3.5%	1.3%	2.4%	37.0%	2.5%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	42.1%	34.7%	38.4%	15.0%	3.9%	2.1%	3.0%	35.4%	2.1%	100.0%
IT - Italy	30.4%	46.1%	38.3%	16.6%	3.8%	0.9%	2.4%	35.9%	2.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	41.9%	34.0%	38.0%	13.9%	5.3%	2.0%	3.7%	34.3%	2.9%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	37.8%	35.3%	36.6%	18.8%	2.8%	1.3%	2.1%	34.5%	4.0%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	33.8%	39.0%	36.4%	19.3%	4.9%	1.1%	3.0%	33.4%	2.0%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	31.5%	40.9%	36.2%	20.9%	2.8%	3.2%	3.0%	33.2%	0.7%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	29.8%	42.5%	36.2%	18.3%	6.2%	1.8%	4.0%	32.2%	1.6%	100.0%
PL - Poland	31.2%	40.5%	35.9%	18.1%	7.1%	1.2%	4.2%	31.7%	2.0%	100.0%
AT - Austria	33.0%	37.9%	35.5%	15.3%	6.8%	3.4%	5.1%	30.4%	3.7%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	40.7%	29.2%	35.0%	15.3%	3.8%	3.3%	3.6%	31.4%	7.7%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	31.2%	36.1%	33.7%	24.4%	4.0%	2.3%	3.2%	30.5%	2.0%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	34.2%	32.1%	33.2%	15.3%	2.9%	1.0%	2.0%	31.2%	14.4%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	33.9%	31.2%	32.6%	17.3%	4.4%	2.8%	3.6%	29.0%	10.5%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	29.6%	34.6%	32.1%	21.4%	6.3%	1.6%	4.0%	28.2%	6.6%	100.0%
RO - Romania	30.5%	33.2%	31.9%	24.9%	7.3%	0.7%	4.0%	27.9%	3.4%	100.0%
AL - Albania	5.6%	24.6%	15.1%	41.9%	12.7%	6.2%	9.5%	5.7%	9.0%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	53.1%	30.9%	42.0%	8.7%	3.6%	1.2%	2.4%	39.6%	2.6%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	43.1%	34.1%	38.6%	13.7%	4.7%	1.7%	3.2%	35.4%	2.7%	100.0%
Germany weighted	51.1%	31.5%	41.3%	9.6%	3.8%	1.3%	2.6%	38.8%	2.6%	100.0%

QA12a.1 (EB 95.2; 2021)				
The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly. Reliable				
Rank-ordered by 'Describes well'				
	Describes well	Describes badly	Don't know	Total
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	86.2%	13.3%	0.5%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	86.1%	12.7%	1.2%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	83.8%	12.9%	3.3%	100.0%
NO - Norway	83.5%	15.5%	1.1%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	83.0%	16.6%	0.4%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	80.5%	18.9%	0.6%	100.0%
FI - Finland	79.4%	19.4%	1.2%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	79.4%	19.8%	0.8%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	79.3%	20.2%	0.5%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	78.9%	15.0%	6.2%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	77.7%	10.0%	12.3%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	76.7%	15.1%	8.2%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	76.1%	23.2%	0.7%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	75.5%	23.3%	1.2%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	75.5%	13.6%	10.9%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	75.0%	24.8%	0.3%	100.0%
ES - Spain	73.6%	15.2%	11.2%	100.0%
PL - Poland	73.1%	14.6%	12.3%	100.0%
IT - Italy	72.0%	21.4%	6.6%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	71.5%	7.3%	21.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	70.4%	20.7%	8.9%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	68.2%	23.4%	8.4%	100.0%
GR - Greece	68.0%	22.7%	9.4%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	67.1%	31.7%	1.2%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	67.1%	14.1%	18.8%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	66.4%	32.1%	1.5%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	64.4%	35.5%	0.1%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	62.6%	29.6%	7.8%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	62.0%	25.4%	12.6%	100.0%
MT - Malta	61.7%	12.4%	25.9%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	60.3%	20.0%	19.8%	100.0%
RO - Romania	59.8%	27.2%	13.0%	100.0%
AT - Austria	59.2%	26.1%	14.7%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	58.7%	23.1%	18.2%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	57.8%	25.1%	17.1%	100.0%
FR - France	57.4%	28.0%	14.6%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	56.2%	22.4%	21.4%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	55.0%	28.5%	16.5%	100.0%
AL - Albania	53.0%	22.9%	24.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	51.2%	27.2%	21.6%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	60.4%	19.8%	19.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	50.3%	27.7%	22.0%	100.0%
Germany weighted	58.5%	21.4%	20.2%	100.0%

QA12a.5 (EB 95.2; 2021)				
The following is a list of characteristics that can be associated with scientists today. For each characteristic, indicate if you think it describes scientists well or describes them badly. Honest				
Rank-ordered by 'Describes well'				
	Describes well	Describes badly	Don't know	Total
TR - Turkey	83.8%	14.4%	1.8%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	82.8%	16.6%	0.5%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	80.6%	18.6%	0.8%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	80.5%	15.4%	4.1%	100.0%
NO - Norway	79.7%	18.9%	1.3%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	77.7%	21.7%	0.6%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	77.5%	22.2%	0.3%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	76.0%	23.6%	0.5%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	75.5%	18.1%	6.4%	100.0%
FI - Finland	75.4%	23.4%	1.2%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	72.8%	26.7%	0.6%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	72.2%	17.6%	10.2%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	71.3%	27.5%	1.2%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	70.9%	14.4%	14.7%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	70.4%	10.5%	19.1%	100.0%
ES - Spain	66.9%	14.4%	18.6%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	65.7%	34.0%	0.3%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	65.4%	34.5%	0.1%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	63.7%	35.2%	1.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	62.9%	24.7%	12.4%	100.0%
IT - Italy	58.9%	26.9%	14.3%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	57.1%	41.6%	1.4%	100.0%
PL - Poland	56.7%	22.3%	21.0%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	56.6%	28.4%	15.1%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	54.9%	35.5%	9.6%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	54.8%	22.2%	23.0%	100.0%
GR - Greece	53.4%	30.5%	16.1%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	53.1%	31.8%	15.2%	100.0%
MT - Malta	52.0%	18.9%	29.1%	100.0%
RO - Romania	50.0%	35.1%	14.9%	100.0%
FR - France	49.3%	30.8%	19.9%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	49.1%	11.7%	39.2%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	48.8%	26.9%	24.3%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	47.8%	29.1%	23.1%	100.0%
AL - Albania	47.6%	24.0%	28.4%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	47.5%	30.3%	22.2%	100.0%
AT - Austria	47.4%	29.8%	22.8%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	47.3%	25.5%	27.3%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	44.6%	29.4%	26.0%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	40.8%	32.7%	26.5%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	48.5%	27.3%	24.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	38.5%	34.4%	27.1%	100.0%
Germany weighted	46.5%	28.7%	24.8%	100.0%

QA9.3 (EB 95.2; 2021)

The following are some statements that people have made about science or technology. For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree. Scientists spend sufficient time meeting people like me to explain their work

Rank-ordered by 'Agree'

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree - disagree	Don't know	Total
ME - Montenegro	13.9%	32.7%	23.3%	17.7%	24.6%	9.5%	17.1%	6.3%	1.6%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	14.6%	28.6%	21.6%	20.7%	11.9%	14.7%	13.3%	8.3%	9.6%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	15.8%	24.2%	20.0%	27.2%	18.5%	14.1%	16.3%	3.7%	0.1%	100.0%
PL - Poland	9.7%	26.4%	18.1%	23.0%	22.6%	15.1%	18.9%	-0.8%	3.1%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	9.9%	24.7%	17.3%	23.0%	16.4%	21.3%	18.9%	-1.6%	4.7%	100.0%
ES - Spain	7.5%	25.3%	16.4%	17.6%	22.3%	21.0%	21.7%	-5.3%	6.3%	100.0%
RO - Romania	9.9%	22.0%	16.0%	28.2%	23.8%	13.9%	18.9%	-2.9%	2.2%	100.0%
IT - Italy	7.4%	24.4%	15.9%	24.8%	26.0%	13.5%	19.8%	-3.9%	3.9%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	4.5%	24.8%	14.7%	28.3%	23.3%	17.0%	20.2%	-5.5%	2.1%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	7.1%	21.6%	14.4%	26.8%	21.3%	16.8%	19.1%	-4.7%	6.5%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	3.0%	22.5%	12.8%	35.5%	30.7%	8.1%	19.4%	-6.7%		100.0%
MT - Malta	2.9%	22.3%	12.6%	24.2%	24.6%	13.7%	19.2%	-6.6%	12.4%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	7.3%	17.4%	12.4%	16.0%	30.4%	24.3%	27.4%	-15.0%	4.5%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	4.4%	20.0%	12.2%	25.8%	26.0%	22.4%	24.2%	-12.0%	1.4%	100.0%
AT - Austria	6.4%	16.5%	11.5%	19.6%	24.2%	30.1%	27.2%	-15.7%	3.3%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	5.0%	17.9%	11.5%	39.1%	25.7%	10.7%	18.2%	-6.8%	1.7%	100.0%
EU+ average	5.5%	17.3%	11.4%	28.0%	28.5%	17.9%	23.2%	-11.8%	2.8%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	8.8%	13.6%	11.2%	19.8%	18.2%	34.2%	26.2%	-15.0%	5.4%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	6.2%	16.0%	11.1%	34.4%	29.6%	13.8%	21.7%	-10.6%		100.0%
SI - Slovenia	5.1%	16.2%	10.7%	23.4%	30.2%	23.3%	26.8%	-16.1%	1.9%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	6.4%	14.8%	10.6%	15.4%	23.4%	26.6%	25.0%	-14.4%	13.4%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	3.7%	16.6%	10.2%	21.6%	33.1%	21.0%	27.1%	-16.9%	4.0%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	3.8%	15.9%	9.9%	29.1%	30.2%	21.0%	25.6%	-15.8%		100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	3.7%	15.4%	9.6%	34.3%	33.6%	10.1%	21.9%	-12.3%	2.8%	100.0%
GR - Greece	6.1%	12.9%	9.5%	17.8%	30.6%	31.3%	31.0%	-21.5%	1.3%	100.0%
FR - France	3.8%	14.1%	9.0%	16.7%	29.4%	33.0%	31.2%	-22.3%	3.1%	100.0%
AL - Albania	4.0%	13.6%	8.8%	41.8%	18.9%	11.0%	15.0%	-6.2%	10.6%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	3.5%	14.1%	8.8%	44.3%	28.0%	10.1%	19.1%	-10.3%		100.0%
FI - Finland	4.3%	12.9%	8.6%	39.9%	29.5%	13.3%	21.4%	-12.8%	0.1%	100.0%
NO - Norway	3.0%	13.3%	8.2%	42.7%	31.5%	9.5%	20.5%	-12.4%		100.0%
BE - Belgium	1.0%	14.9%	8.0%	36.2%	40.7%	7.2%	24.0%	-16.0%		100.0%
IS - Iceland	3.5%	12.4%	8.0%	42.7%	29.3%	12.2%	20.8%	-12.8%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	2.1%	13.7%	7.9%	32.5%	35.8%	16.0%	25.9%	-18.0%		100.0%
LV - Latvia	2.5%	12.9%	7.7%	28.7%	36.4%	19.5%	28.0%	-20.3%		100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	1.6%	11.9%	6.8%	30.2%	44.6%	11.6%	28.1%	-21.4%	0.1%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	2.6%	10.4%	6.5%	18.6%	30.1%	35.3%	32.7%	-26.2%	3.1%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	2.5%	10.1%	6.3%	28.1%	44.7%	14.6%	29.7%	-23.4%		100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	1.6%	10.9%	6.3%	34.4%	42.3%	10.7%	26.5%	-20.3%		100.0%
IE - Ireland	2.4%	10.0%	6.2%	31.7%	43.0%	13.0%	28.0%	-21.8%		100.0%
DE-E Germany East	1.8%	8.2%	5.0%	22.7%	27.2%	36.6%	31.9%	-26.9%	3.5%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	2.8%	10.3%	6.6%	18.2%	30.8%	34.7%	32.8%	-26.2%	3.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	1.3%	7.7%	4.5%	22.4%	26.4%	38.8%	32.6%	-28.1%	3.3%	100.0%
Germany weighted	2.5%	9.8%	6.2%	19.0%	30.0%	35.5%	32.8%	-26.6%	3.2%	100.0%

QC4 (EB 73.1; 2010)

Which of the following public involvement do you think is appropriate when it comes to decisions about science and technology?

Rank-ordered by 'The public should be consulted and public opinion should only be considered when making decisions about science and technology'

	The public does not need to be involved in decisions about science and technology	Decisions about science and technology should be made by scientists, engineers and politicians, and the public should be informed about these decisions	The public should be consulted and public opinion should only be considered when making decisions about science and technology	Public opinion should be binding when making decisions about science and technology	NGOs should be partners in scientific and technological research	None	Don't know	Total
DK - Denmark	3.9%	35.0%	45.4%	7.3%	6.2%	0.4%	1.9%	100.0%
FI - Finland	7.8%	32.9%	43.4%	7.1%	7.3%	0.5%	1.1%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	4.8%	27.2%	43.1%	11.2%	9.0%	1.1%	3.6%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.8%	35.9%	39.9%	11.3%	6.0%	1.7%	1.3%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	4.5%	29.9%	39.4%	12.3%	8.1%	2.8%	3.0%	100.0%
FR - France	6.2%	26.8%	36.1%	15.4%	9.1%	1.4%	4.9%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	5.0%	46.8%	34.5%	5.2%	5.6%	0.8%	2.2%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	7.4%	38.0%	34.4%	11.7%	5.2%	0.8%	2.6%	100.0%
AT - Austria	6.8%	31.0%	32.8%	13.0%	12.1%	1.6%	2.7%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	6.3%	32.6%	32.3%	14.6%	6.8%	0.6%	6.7%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	10.6%	34.8%	30.4%	11.9%	7.2%	4.0%	1.2%	100.0%
MT - Malta	6.2%	43.2%	30.4%	8.0%	3.4%		8.8%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	4.4%	49.0%	30.2%	3.4%	10.0%	0.5%	2.6%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	6.4%	43.7%	29.0%	9.2%	1.7%	0.8%	9.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	6.8%	40.2%	27.6%	12.3%	6.8%	1.3%	5.0%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	7.0%	42.7%	26.9%	3.2%	15.0%	3.2%	2.0%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	6.8%	42.2%	25.6%	17.9%	3.9%	1.1%	2.6%	100.0%
NO - Norway	4.7%	53.6%	25.6%	5.2%	7.1%	0.7%	3.1%	100.0%
NI - Northern Ireland	6.0%	33.8%	25.2%	14.2%	5.6%	3.0%	12.3%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	8.3%	45.0%	25.2%	12.2%	3.9%	1.5%	3.8%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	7.6%	39.4%	24.1%	14.4%	9.6%	1.7%	3.2%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	5.8%	45.4%	23.7%	13.1%	5.4%	0.9%	5.7%	100.0%
PL - Poland	10.6%	29.3%	23.4%	15.4%	8.8%	1.3%	11.2%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	6.3%	43.5%	23.2%	16.6%	3.1%	0.2%	7.1%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	10.8%	42.2%	23.2%	8.9%	3.7%	1.8%	9.5%	100.0%
GR - Greece	3.7%	52.9%	22.9%	15.9%	2.8%	0.5%	1.3%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	3.2%	56.4%	22.9%	10.6%	1.8%	0.2%	5.0%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	6.8%	42.8%	20.5%	15.0%	8.1%	0.9%	5.9%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	6.4%	38.9%	20.5%	21.3%	4.9%	1.9%	6.1%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	11.6%	33.0%	20.1%	14.2%	8.7%	2.2%	10.2%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	7.5%	46.7%	19.9%	14.0%	9.0%	1.0%	1.9%	100.0%
RO - Romania	9.0%	42.8%	19.5%	8.9%	3.4%	1.7%	14.7%	100.0%
IT - Italy	7.5%	40.7%	19.4%	17.5%	7.8%	2.8%	4.4%	100.0%
ES - Spain	6.4%	40.1%	19.2%	16.9%	9.3%	1.4%	6.7%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	7.7%	50.0%	13.9%	14.4%	11.0%	0.3%	2.8%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	4.8%	27.1%	43.6%	10.1%	9.8%	0.9%	3.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.3%	34.8%	41.4%	10.8%	6.3%	2.1%	1.2%	100.0%
Germany weighted	4.5%	28.8%	43.1%	10.3%	9.0%	1.2%	3.1%	100.0%

QD6 (EB 79.2; 2013)

What is the level of involvement citizens should have when it comes to decisions made about science and technology?

Rank-ordered by 'Citizens should be consulted & their opinion considered'

	Citizens do not need to be involved or informed	Citizens should only be informed	Citizens should be consulted & their opinion considered	Citizens should participate and have an active role	Citizens' opinions should be binding	None	Total
MT - Malta	6.7%	16.2%	56.2%	17.2%	3.2%	0.5%	100.0%
GB-NIR Northern Ireland	4.4%	30.9%	53.7%	10.3%	0.4%	0.4%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	4.1%	19.9%	53.3%	18.9%	3.4%	0.4%	100.0%
GB-GBN - Great Britain	6.9%	24.7%	53.3%	11.5%	2.8%	0.7%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.8%	25.1%	51.2%	15.1%	3.4%	1.4%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.4%	26.5%	49.4%	15.2%	4.4%	1.1%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	2.7%	32.5%	48.3%	11.9%	3.9%	0.8%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	2.8%	27.8%	46.7%	21.1%	1.1%	0.4%	100.0%
FR - France	3.8%	34.2%	45.3%	13.1%	1.9%	1.8%	100.0%
FI - Finland	4.1%	35.8%	41.3%	14.4%	4.2%	0.3%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	4.3%	34.0%	39.8%	17.5%	3.8%	0.6%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	9.1%	38.7%	39.1%	8.0%	2.7%	2.3%	100.0%
EU+ average	6.4%	35.2%	38.2%	14.1%	4.5%	1.7%	100.0%
PL - Poland	5.9%	40.2%	37.5%	10.6%	5.0%	0.7%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	6.8%	41.9%	37.4%	6.4%	2.1%	5.3%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	6.1%	36.2%	37.3%	11.6%	7.9%	0.9%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	11.8%	30.0%	37.2%	15.8%	3.2%	2.0%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	8.3%	39.5%	36.7%	11.1%	2.4%	2.0%	100.0%
AT - Austria	7.6%	31.4%	36.3%	14.1%	8.0%	2.5%	100.0%
IT - Italy	8.2%	39.5%	35.9%	9.9%	4.3%	2.2%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	4.8%	33.0%	34.8%	17.7%	3.8%	5.9%	100.0%
ES - Spain	8.2%	34.9%	34.0%	13.7%	7.9%	1.2%	100.0%
RO - Romania	9.8%	36.8%	33.4%	12.7%	3.3%	4.1%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	6.6%	43.7%	31.4%	11.3%	5.7%	1.4%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	7.3%	45.1%	30.4%	9.2%	6.8%	1.4%	100.0%
GR - Greece	4.2%	34.5%	29.9%	24.0%	7.1%	0.3%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	5.8%	41.3%	29.8%	13.0%	7.9%	2.1%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	7.8%	47.0%	29.5%	11.8%	3.3%	0.5%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	7.4%	32.2%	28.5%	20.9%	8.8%	2.3%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	1.7%	36.7%	28.3%	27.7%	4.8%	0.8%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	10.9%	45.7%	25.3%	13.6%	2.7%	1.7%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.9%	24.6%	51.2%	15.7%	3.1%	1.4%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.5%	27.7%	49.8%	14.1%	3.9%	1.0%	100.0%
Germany weighted	3.8%	25.2%	50.9%	15.4%	3.3%	1.3%	100.0%

QA7 (EB 95.2; 2021)

What level of public involvement do you think is appropriate when it comes to decisions about science and technology?

Rank-ordered by 'The public should be consulted and public opinion should be seriously considered when making decisions about science and technology'

	The public does not need to be involved in decisions about science and technology	Decisions about science and technology should be made by scientists, engineers and politicians, but the public should always be informed	The public should be consulted and public opinion should be seriously considered when making decisions about science and technology	Public opinion should be the main concern when making decisions about science and technology	Other	Don't know	Total
CH - Switzerland	2.0%	48.1%	44.7%	5.1%		0.1%	100.0%
FR - France	4.7%	42.0%	42.3%	10.0%	0.2%	0.8%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	2.9%	53.4%	40.9%	2.9%			100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.3%	42.4%	38.9%	13.2%	0.7%	1.5%	100.0%
AT - Austria	12.1%	36.9%	37.3%	12.6%	0.5%	0.5%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	5.0%	52.8%	36.8%	4.8%	0.2%	0.5%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	3.4%	58.5%	35.9%	2.2%			100.0%
FI - Finland	6.3%	55.0%	35.8%	2.6%	0.2%	0.1%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	5.5%	56.0%	35.4%	2.5%	0.2%	0.4%	100.0%
RO - Romania	4.3%	38.8%	35.0%	19.9%	0.2%	1.9%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	10.3%	49.6%	31.5%	8.1%		0.5%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	2.6%	61.7%	31.4%	4.2%	0.1%		100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	3.1%	62.7%	30.9%	3.2%	0.1%	0.1%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	4.6%	59.2%	30.8%	5.4%			100.0%
HU - Hungary	8.0%	54.5%	30.6%	6.5%		0.5%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	6.2%	59.9%	30.4%	3.2%		0.2%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	9.2%	54.0%	30.3%	5.3%	0.1%	1.1%	100.0%
NO - Norway	4.8%	61.0%	30.1%	4.0%		0.1%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	8.4%	53.2%	29.8%	8.7%			100.0%
SI - Slovenia	9.7%	52.2%	29.4%	8.3%	0.1%	0.3%	100.0%
EU+ average	7.6%	55.6%	29.3%	6.6%	0.1%	0.7%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	17.2%	44.7%	29.1%	8.4%	0.3%	0.4%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	13.0%	44.3%	28.9%	11.2%	0.1%	2.5%	100.0%
MT - Malta	2.7%	60.4%	27.8%	6.5%		2.7%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	6.5%	60.4%	27.6%	5.4%			100.0%
PL - Poland	12.1%	49.7%	27.4%	9.6%		1.2%	100.0%
IT - Italy	10.1%	55.6%	26.3%	6.9%		1.1%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	7.5%	62.7%	26.1%	2.7%		1.0%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	11.7%	45.9%	25.6%	10.0%	0.2%	6.6%	100.0%
ES - Spain	8.1%	57.3%	25.0%	7.3%	0.1%	2.3%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	3.0%	68.1%	24.5%	4.2%		0.2%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	9.3%	58.8%	24.4%	7.5%		0.1%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	9.0%	64.6%	23.0%	3.4%			100.0%
ME - Montenegro	17.9%	54.4%	21.6%	6.2%			100.0%
EE - Estonia	3.9%	72.1%	21.5%	2.3%	0.2%		100.0%
GR - Greece	13.9%	54.7%	21.3%	9.6%		0.5%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	6.8%	71.7%	19.9%	1.4%	0.1%		100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	6.9%	62.1%	17.2%	11.9%	0.4%	1.6%	100.0%
AL - Albania	7.3%	69.5%	15.5%	7.6%		0.1%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	13.1%	63.6%	15.1%	7.5%	0.2%	0.6%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	5.1%	53.2%	36.7%	4.4%	0.2%	0.5%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	3.0%	40.5%	40.1%	14.0%	0.7%	1.7%	100.0%
Germany weighted	4.7%	50.7%	37.4%	6.3%	0.3%	0.7%	100.0%

QA14.1 (EB 95.2; 2021)

And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues. Do you: Talk about science and technology-related issues with family or friends?

Rank-ordered by 'Yes, regularly'

	Yes, regularly	Yes, occasionally	Hardly ever	No, never	Don't know	Total
NL - The Netherlands	30.7%	43.5%	16.4%	9.4%		100.0%
PT - Portugal	29.1%	55.3%	12.3%	3.3%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	29.1%	49.1%	18.7%	3.1%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	27.9%	54.6%	14.8%	2.7%		100.0%
TR - Turkey	27.3%	46.0%	13.4%	13.2%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	26.6%	44.2%	17.3%	11.6%	0.3%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	26.5%	45.4%	18.5%	9.1%	0.5%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	26.5%	51.8%	16.6%	5.0%		100.0%
SE - Sweden	24.3%	53.9%	15.1%	6.7%		100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	23.1%	52.9%	18.1%	6.0%		100.0%
BE - Belgium	22.2%	52.6%	19.9%	5.3%		100.0%
EE - Estonia	19.9%	63.6%	12.5%	4.0%		100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	18.8%	37.7%	13.2%	30.0%	0.2%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	18.7%	49.9%	27.2%	4.2%		100.0%
NO - Norway	18.3%	51.8%	21.8%	8.1%		100.0%
FR - France	17.9%	40.5%	14.8%	26.7%	0.1%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	17.2%	54.1%	20.5%	8.3%		100.0%
ES - Spain	16.9%	28.6%	13.4%	40.4%	0.6%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	16.8%	41.1%	22.1%	19.9%	0.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	16.0%	43.4%	18.5%	21.4%	0.7%	100.0%
FI - Finland	14.8%	57.3%	20.6%	7.4%		100.0%
LV - Latvia	14.1%	57.0%	19.7%	9.0%	0.1%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	13.7%	32.5%	17.8%	33.4%	2.6%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	13.1%	63.4%	14.3%	9.1%		100.0%
AT - Austria	12.6%	33.9%	27.9%	25.3%	0.3%	100.0%
GR - Greece	12.4%	44.4%	17.2%	26.0%	0.1%	100.0%
MT - Malta	10.3%	49.9%	12.6%	23.8%	3.4%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	10.1%	40.6%	18.0%	31.3%	0.1%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	9.3%	45.4%	17.5%	27.7%	0.2%	100.0%
AL - Albania	9.2%	26.8%	24.6%	33.9%	5.5%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	8.3%	27.4%	27.6%	35.3%	1.5%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	8.2%	38.3%	21.1%	31.7%	0.7%	100.0%
RO - Romania	8.1%	30.2%	27.8%	33.5%	0.4%	100.0%
IT - Italy	7.7%	29.9%	15.2%	46.7%	0.6%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	6.9%	43.6%	18.6%	30.7%	0.2%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	6.8%	40.0%	14.7%	36.8%	1.8%	100.0%
PL - Poland	6.7%	26.5%	20.3%	45.8%	0.8%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	5.0%	33.8%	20.5%	37.0%	3.7%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	4.4%	28.2%	17.3%	47.9%	2.3%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	4.2%	30.2%	17.9%	47.6%	0.2%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	27.6%	44.4%	18.1%	9.5%	0.5%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	16.7%	41.8%	23.4%	17.7%	0.3%	100.0%
Germany weighted	25.4%	43.9%	19.1%	11.1%	0.5%	100.0%

QA14.6 (EB 95.2; 2021)

And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues. Do you: Attend public meetings or debates about science and technology?

Rank-ordered by 'Yes, regularly'

	Yes, regularly	Yes, occasionally	Hardly ever	No, never	Don't know	Total
TR - Turkey	15.3%	26.0%	27.5%	31.1%	0.1%	100.0%
AL - Albania	9.4%	10.9%	31.9%	42.0%	5.8%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	8.4%	16.9%	20.0%	51.8%	2.8%	100.0%
AT - Austria	6.3%	14.8%	14.6%	64.0%	0.4%	100.0%
RO - Romania	5.0%	13.6%	16.6%	64.0%	0.8%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	4.2%	8.1%	12.8%	74.5%	0.4%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	3.9%	10.2%	20.0%	65.3%	0.6%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	3.8%	17.9%	36.6%	41.7%		100.0%
IT - Italy	3.5%	11.8%	13.9%	70.3%	0.5%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.2%	13.6%	24.3%	57.9%	1.0%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	3.0%	8.3%	13.3%	73.6%	1.8%	100.0%
EU+ average	3.0%	11.8%	24.3%	60.1%	0.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	2.9%	6.8%	18.5%	71.3%	0.4%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	2.8%	11.2%	15.7%	68.0%	2.3%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	2.6%	14.9%	28.6%	53.9%		100.0%
LV - Latvia	2.6%	17.0%	29.6%	50.9%		100.0%
ES - Spain	2.4%	7.1%	8.4%	82.1%	0.1%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	2.4%	14.8%	36.4%	46.4%		100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	2.4%	14.5%	41.6%	41.5%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	2.4%	20.9%	37.9%	38.9%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	2.3%	20.4%	37.5%	39.8%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	2.2%	12.2%	26.1%	58.9%	0.6%	100.0%
PL - Poland	2.2%	7.6%	11.9%	77.6%	0.7%	100.0%
FR - France	2.1%	9.5%	11.8%	76.4%	0.3%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	2.1%	9.8%	26.9%	60.7%	0.5%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	1.9%	7.7%	17.9%	72.4%	0.2%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	1.8%	14.8%	41.0%	42.3%		100.0%
HU - Hungary	1.8%	6.4%	18.8%	72.3%	0.7%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	1.7%	9.6%	31.2%	57.5%		100.0%
GR - Greece	1.5%	13.2%	19.0%	66.1%	0.3%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	1.5%	7.6%	30.1%	60.8%		100.0%
IS - Iceland	1.5%	7.5%	28.4%	62.5%		100.0%
SI - Slovenia	1.4%	10.3%	22.4%	65.8%	0.2%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	1.4%	6.1%	13.0%	76.1%	3.4%	100.0%
NO - Norway	1.1%	9.8%	32.0%	57.2%		100.0%
SK - Slovakia	1.0%	5.7%	20.3%	71.5%	1.5%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	0.9%	12.7%	34.8%	51.6%		100.0%
MT - Malta	0.8%	11.2%	20.2%	64.4%	3.4%	100.0%
FI - Finland	0.6%	9.0%	39.1%	51.3%		100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	0.6%	5.2%	10.2%	82.7%	1.2%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.3%	13.9%	25.1%	56.4%	1.1%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	2.3%	7.0%	18.0%	72.0%	0.7%	100.0%
Germany weighted	3.1%	12.6%	23.7%	59.5%	1.0%	100.0%

QA14.12 (EB 95.2; 2021)

And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues. Do you: Actively take part in scientific projects by developing research questions, collecting data, discussing the findings with others, etc?

Rank-ordered by 'Yes, regularly'

	Yes, regularly	Yes, occasionally	Hardly ever	No, never	Don't know	Total
TR - Turkey	16.4%	29.6%	21.3%	32.6%	0.1%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	7.0%	13.6%	15.0%	64.3%	0.2%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	6.9%	10.8%	17.9%	60.7%	3.6%	100.0%
AL - Albania	6.8%	11.9%	33.4%	43.1%	4.7%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	6.5%	16.7%	28.7%	48.1%		100.0%
AT - Austria	6.0%	14.7%	9.7%	68.3%	1.3%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	5.7%	13.9%	19.7%	60.7%		100.0%
PT - Portugal	5.6%	16.8%	28.8%	48.8%		100.0%
LT - Lithuania	5.6%	16.6%	24.5%	53.2%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	4.9%	12.4%	16.7%	65.5%	0.5%	100.0%
RO - Romania	4.7%	14.7%	17.0%	62.9%	0.8%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	4.5%	15.1%	24.9%	55.5%		100.0%
LV - Latvia	4.5%	12.5%	24.2%	58.8%		100.0%
IS - Iceland	4.4%	14.5%	19.5%	61.6%		100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	4.4%	13.3%	19.5%	61.9%	0.9%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	4.0%	6.1%	9.5%	79.6%	0.8%	100.0%
EU+ average	4.0%	11.4%	17.9%	65.9%	0.8%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	3.9%	10.9%	20.0%	65.2%		100.0%
BE - Belgium	3.6%	14.9%	25.0%	56.5%		100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.5%	8.1%	11.9%	74.8%	1.7%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	3.4%	14.8%	28.2%	53.6%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	3.3%	11.1%	21.1%	64.5%		100.0%
PL - Poland	3.2%	7.1%	8.6%	80.4%	0.7%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	3.2%	6.9%	15.3%	72.5%	2.1%	100.0%
IT - Italy	3.1%	8.3%	13.4%	74.4%	0.8%	100.0%
FR - France	3.0%	7.3%	7.7%	81.7%	0.4%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	3.0%	11.5%	20.9%	64.6%		100.0%
MT - Malta	2.9%	12.2%	17.1%	64.2%	3.6%	100.0%
FI - Finland	2.8%	13.5%	32.4%	51.3%		100.0%
NO - Norway	2.7%	13.0%	20.7%	63.7%		100.0%
ME - Montenegro	2.6%	9.3%	13.5%	73.8%	0.8%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	2.4%	10.6%	14.9%	71.8%	0.3%	100.0%
ES - Spain	2.2%	4.0%	6.4%	87.0%	0.5%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	2.2%	6.0%	6.2%	85.0%	0.7%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	2.0%	11.5%	21.3%	64.6%	0.7%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	1.6%	6.6%	11.5%	76.5%	3.8%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	1.5%	5.9%	17.3%	74.4%	0.9%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	1.4%	7.1%	14.0%	76.1%	1.4%	100.0%
GR - Greece	0.8%	4.4%	8.5%	86.0%	0.4%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	0.5%	3.3%	6.5%	88.6%	1.1%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	3.6%	8.7%	12.6%	73.3%	1.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	1.7%	6.3%	6.0%	85.3%	0.7%	100.0%
Germany weighted	3.2%	8.3%	11.3%	75.7%	1.5%	100.0%

QC1 (EB 73.1; 2010)					
In everyday life, we have to deal with many different problems and situations, where we feel more or less interested and confident. I am going to read you a number of statements. For each of them, please tell me whether you are [interested in]... Environmental problems					
Rank-ordered by 'Very interested'					
	Very interested	Moderately interested	Not at all interested	Don't know	Total
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	64.1%	30.1%	5.8%		100.0%
MT - Malta	59.0%	36.2%	3.8%	1.0%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	58.4%	37.2%	4.4%		100.0%
CH - Switzerland	56.1%	39.6%	4.2%	0.1%	100.0%
GR - Greece	55.1%	39.2%	5.7%		100.0%
FR - France	54.1%	39.5%	6.4%		100.0%
SE - Sweden	50.3%	45.5%	4.2%		100.0%
HU - Hungary	49.4%	44.0%	6.6%	0.1%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	45.6%	48.4%	6.0%		100.0%
DE-E Germany East	41.8%	50.9%	7.4%		100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	40.7%	49.4%	9.6%	0.3%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	40.6%	47.6%	11.7%	0.1%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	39.6%	51.8%	8.5%	0.1%	100.0%
FI - Finland	39.1%	54.7%	6.1%	0.1%	100.0%
ES - Spain	38.8%	51.6%	9.0%	0.6%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	38.6%	51.2%	9.8%	0.4%	100.0%
NO - Norway	38.5%	54.7%	6.7%	0.2%	100.0%
AT - Austria	37.7%	49.2%	12.9%	0.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	36.3%	51.4%	11.6%	0.6%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	36.2%	56.6%	7.0%	0.3%	100.0%
NI - Northern Ireland	35.4%	48.7%	15.2%	0.7%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	34.4%	54.9%	10.6%	0.2%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	34.4%	49.0%	15.5%	1.1%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	31.7%	59.5%	8.7%	0.2%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	31.5%	51.9%	15.2%	1.4%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	30.4%	59.3%	10.0%	0.3%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	28.8%	60.9%	10.2%	0.2%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	28.7%	58.5%	12.8%		100.0%
PT - Portugal	22.3%	57.8%	18.5%	1.4%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	21.1%	58.5%	18.5%	1.9%	100.0%
IT - Italy	20.6%	60.1%	17.6%	1.7%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	19.6%	46.5%	31.0%	2.9%	100.0%
RO - Romania	18.4%	55.8%	22.5%	3.4%	100.0%
PL - Poland	18.2%	60.5%	20.5%	0.8%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	11.2%	64.6%	23.5%	0.7%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	46.6%	48.0%	5.3%		100.0%
DE-E Germany East	40.8%	51.7%	7.5%		100.0%
Germany weighted	45.4%	48.8%	5.8%		100.0%

QA2.6 (EB 95.2; 2021)					
In everyday life, we have to deal with many different issues, where we feel more or less interested. For each of the following, please indicate whether you are [interested in]...					
Environmental problems including climate change					
Rank-ordered by 'Very interested'					
	Very interested	Moderately interested	Not at all interested	Don't know	Total
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	70.4%	24.7%	4.3%	0.6%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	67.2%	31.6%	1.2%		100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	60.2%	35.6%	4.1%	0.1%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	59.7%	36.7%	3.6%		100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	58.1%	37.9%	4.0%		100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	57.6%	38.9%	3.4%	0.1%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	55.6%	40.9%	3.5%		100.0%
FR - France	54.3%	36.7%	8.7%	0.4%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	53.7%	42.1%	4.2%		100.0%
MT - Malta	50.3%	43.0%	5.0%	1.7%	100.0%
ES - Spain	49.9%	41.9%	8.2%		100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	48.9%	46.5%	4.5%		100.0%
GR - Greece	45.8%	44.3%	10.0%		100.0%
AT - Austria	44.1%	45.8%	10.0%	0.1%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	43.4%	44.4%	12.1%	0.1%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	40.8%	51.8%	7.4%		100.0%
DK - Denmark	39.7%	50.3%	9.8%	0.2%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	38.5%	55.2%	6.3%		100.0%
DE-E Germany East	38.0%	52.3%	9.1%	0.7%	100.0%
EU+ average	37.6%	50.1%	11.8%	0.5%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	37.5%	56.3%	6.2%		100.0%
SK - Slovakia	37.0%	46.3%	16.4%	0.3%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	35.3%	51.3%	13.4%		100.0%
FI - Finland	34.4%	55.1%	10.5%		100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	33.5%	49.2%	15.5%	1.8%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	32.5%	55.3%	11.6%	0.6%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	31.7%	52.7%	15.1%	0.6%	100.0%
RO - Romania	30.1%	53.2%	16.1%	0.6%	100.0%
NO - Norway	29.7%	61.4%	8.9%		100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	28.9%	51.6%	18.6%	0.9%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	27.6%	61.5%	10.4%	0.5%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	26.6%	59.8%	13.5%	0.1%	100.0%
IT - Italy	18.5%	63.2%	17.6%	0.7%	100.0%
PL - Poland	18.0%	57.9%	23.8%	0.3%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	16.5%	60.4%	22.1%	1.1%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	16.2%	55.9%	27.2%	0.7%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	15.1%	59.9%	21.9%	3.1%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	15.0%	68.5%	16.5%		100.0%
ME - Montenegro	14.7%	65.1%	20.0%	0.2%	100.0%
AL - Albania	6.7%	59.4%	29.9%	4.0%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	60.2%	35.7%	4.0%	0.1%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	37.1%	52.2%	10.4%	0.3%	100.0%
Germany weighted	55.7%	38.9%	5.2%	0.1%	100.0%

QA20.9 (EB 95.2; 2021)

Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so. Climate change is for the most part caused by natural cycles rather than human activities.

Rank-ordered by 'Correct'

	True (Incorrect)	False (Correct)	Don't know	Correct - Incorrect	Total
PT - Portugal	11.5%	84.8%	3.7%	73.3%	100.0%
NL - The Netherlands	14.4%	79.2%	6.4%	64.8%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	14.0%	77.2%	8.8%	63.2%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	15.3%	77.5%	7.1%	62.2%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	13.1%	73.2%	13.7%	60.1%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	15.4%	73.7%	10.8%	58.3%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	17.5%	73.7%	8.9%	56.2%	100.0%
FI - Finland	16.5%	72.3%	11.2%	55.8%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	18.6%	72.4%	9.0%	53.8%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	19.0%	71.2%	9.8%	52.2%	100.0%
ES - Spain	21.0%	69.9%	9.1%	48.9%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	18.0%	66.5%	15.4%	48.5%	100.0%
MT - Malta	18.5%	64.8%	16.8%	46.3%	100.0%
NO - Norway	19.9%	64.8%	15.3%	44.9%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	24.1%	69.0%	6.9%	44.9%	100.0%
FR - France	23.6%	67.3%	9.1%	43.7%	100.0%
GR - Greece	25.7%	67.1%	7.2%	41.4%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	23.6%	64.8%	11.6%	41.2%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	23.7%	64.7%	11.6%	41.0%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	23.8%	59.0%	17.2%	35.2%	100.0%
EU+ average	27.7%	61.3%	11.0%	33.6%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	30.1%	62.3%	7.6%	32.2%	100.0%
IT - Italy	31.6%	62.3%	6.1%	30.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	30.2%	60.5%	9.3%	30.3%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	32.0%	61.7%	6.4%	29.7%	100.0%
AT - Austria	31.0%	59.4%	9.6%	28.4%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	30.6%	58.0%	11.4%	27.4%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	31.4%	56.8%	11.8%	25.4%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	32.1%	56.1%	11.8%	24.0%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	29.6%	50.9%	19.4%	21.3%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	34.9%	55.9%	9.2%	21.0%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	34.1%	54.5%	11.4%	20.4%	100.0%
PL - Poland	35.2%	54.1%	10.7%	18.9%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	37.9%	54.8%	7.3%	16.9%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	39.1%	52.3%	8.6%	13.2%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	42.2%	46.8%	11.0%	4.6%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	47.8%	46.7%	5.5%	-1.1%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	36.9%	35.5%	27.6%	-1.4%	100.0%
RO - Romania	48.3%	41.0%	10.7%	-7.3%	100.0%
AL - Albania	57.2%	20.5%	22.3%	-36.7%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	18.4%	72.6%	9.1%	54.2%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	29.4%	61.5%	9.0%	32.1%	100.0%
Germany weighted	20.5%	70.4%	9.0%	49.9%	100.0%

QA20.11 (EB 95.2; 2021)					
Finally, for each of the following statements, please indicate whether you believe them to be true or false. If you don't know, you can just indicate so. Viruses have been produced in government laboratories to control our freedom.					
Rank-ordered by 'Correct-Incorrect'					
	True (Incorrect)	False (Correct)	Don't know	Correct - incorrect	
NL - The Netherlands	6.0%	86.8%	7.3%	80.8%	100.0%
DK - Denmark	6.4%	82.4%	11.2%	76.0%	100.0%
BE - Belgium	8.3%	78.0%	13.7%	69.7%	100.0%
SE - Sweden	7.3%	75.2%	17.5%	67.9%	100.0%
NO - Norway	8.1%	74.5%	17.4%	66.4%	100.0%
CH - Switzerland	8.3%	73.5%	18.2%	65.2%	100.0%
GB-UKM - United Kingdom	9.9%	73.9%	16.1%	64.0%	100.0%
IE - Ireland	9.9%	72.9%	17.2%	63.0%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	11.8%	74.1%	14.1%	62.3%	100.0%
FI - Finland	10.5%	68.6%	20.9%	58.1%	100.0%
LU - Luxembourg	11.7%	69.0%	19.2%	57.3%	100.0%
IS - Iceland	11.4%	64.5%	24.1%	53.1%	100.0%
CZ - Czech Republic	14.3%	66.3%	19.5%	52.0%	100.0%
AT - Austria	23.4%	63.7%	12.9%	40.3%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	21.0%	57.4%	21.6%	36.4%	100.0%
PT - Portugal	18.1%	50.8%	31.0%	32.7%	100.0%
EE - Estonia	20.2%	52.3%	27.5%	32.1%	100.0%
FR - France	29.0%	55.0%	16.1%	26.0%	100.0%
EU+ average	30.7%	49.8%	19.5%	19.1%	100.0%
IT - Italy	34.3%	50.9%	14.9%	16.6%	100.0%
LV - Latvia	28.8%	43.1%	28.2%	14.3%	100.0%
LT - Lithuania	30.8%	40.3%	28.9%	9.5%	100.0%
SK - Slovakia	37.8%	44.7%	17.4%	6.9%	100.0%
ES - Spain	35.8%	42.5%	21.7%	6.7%	100.0%
PL - Poland	39.8%	40.5%	19.7%	0.7%	100.0%
HU - Hungary	42.6%	42.9%	14.6%	0.3%	100.0%
MT - Malta	36.6%	33.0%	30.5%	-3.6%	100.0%
SI - Slovenia	47.1%	35.6%	17.3%	-11.5%	100.0%
GR - Greece	44.2%	32.2%	23.6%	-12.0%	100.0%
RO - Romania	52.2%	33.3%	14.5%	-18.9%	100.0%
HR - Croatia	49.2%	28.0%	22.8%	-21.2%	100.0%
RS - Serbia	52.7%	29.0%	18.3%	-23.7%	100.0%
BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina	52.8%	29.1%	18.0%	-23.7%	100.0%
TR - Turkey	49.5%	25.7%	24.8%	-23.8%	100.0%
CY - Cyprus (Republic)	51.4%	25.9%	22.7%	-25.5%	100.0%
AL - Albania	53.7%	23.3%	23.0%	-30.4%	100.0%
BG - Bulgaria	52.0%	19.0%	29.1%	-33.0%	100.0%
MK - North Macedonia	58.7%	24.8%	16.5%	-33.9%	100.0%
RS-KM - Kosovo	54.1%	18.0%	27.9%	-36.1%	100.0%
ME - Montenegro	70.6%	22.0%	7.3%	-48.6%	100.0%
DE-W - Germany West	11.5%	74.2%	14.3%	62.7%	100.0%
DE-E Germany East	22.1%	54.5%	23.4%	32.4%	100.0%
Germany weighted	13.6%	70.4%	16.1%	56.8%	100.0%

WGM (2018) Q24, 25, and 26 (vaccine hesitancy index)			
Rank-ordered by 'No hesitance'			
	No hesitance	Hesitance	Total
NCyprus	85.3%	14.7%	100.0%
Norway	81.7%	18.3%	100.0%
Poland	77.2%	22.8%	100.0%
Spain	77.0%	23.0%	100.0%
Hungary	76.3%	23.7%	100.0%
United Kingdom	75.9%	24.1%	100.0%
Ireland	75.9%	24.1%	100.0%
Greece	75.7%	24.3%	100.0%
Slovakia	75.2%	24.8%	100.0%
Malta	74.2%	25.8%	100.0%
Italy	71.7%	28.3%	100.0%
Finland	71.1%	28.9%	100.0%
Slovenia	71.0%	29.0%	100.0%
Cyprus	70.7%	29.3%	100.0%
Sweden	70.2%	29.8%	100.0%
Bosnia and Herzegovina	69.5%	30.5%	100.0%
Denmark	67.5%	32.5%	100.0%
Luxembourg	67.4%	32.6%	100.0%
Netherlands	66.2%	33.8%	100.0%
Kosovo	65.1%	34.9%	100.0%
Serbia	65.0%	35.0%	100.0%
Germany	64.5%	35.5%	100.0%
Iceland	62.8%	37.2%	100.0%
Czech Republic	62.4%	37.6%	100.0%
Average	62.3%	37.7%	100.0%
Portugal	62.0%	38.0%	100.0%
Romania	61.6%	38.4%	100.0%
Albania	61.4%	38.6%	100.0%
Belgium	60.3%	39.7%	100.0%
Lithuania	59.4%	40.6%	100.0%
Croatia	56.8%	43.2%	100.0%
Macedonia	54.0%	46.0%	100.0%
Austria	50.4%	49.6%	100.0%
Switzerland	49.7%	50.3%	100.0%
Estonia	48.0%	52.0%	100.0%
France	47.7%	52.3%	100.0%
Montenegro	43.6%	56.4%	100.0%
Russia	42.9%	57.1%	100.0%
Moldova	41.0%	59.0%	100.0%
Latvia	39.0%	61.0%	100.0%
Bulgaria	38.8%	61.2%	100.0%
Belarus	36.9%	63.1%	100.0%
Ukraine	30.8%	69.2%	100.0%

WGM (2020) WP21768			
Vaccines are given to people to help prevent specific diseases.			
If a vaccine to prevent coronavirus was available right now at no cost, would you agree to be vaccinated?			
Rank-ordered by 'No hesitance'			
	No hesitance	Hesitance	Total
Denmark	85.8%	14.2%	100.0%
United Kingdom	76.0%	24.0%	100.0%
Norway	75.7%	24.3%	100.0%
Germany	75.2%	24.8%	100.0%
Ireland	70.1%	29.9%	100.0%
Malta	68.6%	31.4%	100.0%
Finland	66.4%	33.6%	100.0%
Italy	66.4%	33.6%	100.0%
Portugal	66.4%	33.6%	100.0%
Sweden	66.3%	33.7%	100.0%
Netherlands	65.1%	34.9%	100.0%
Austria	62.6%	37.4%	100.0%
Slovenia	57.9%	42.1%	100.0%
France	56.0%	44.0%	100.0%
Switzerland	55.6%	44.4%	100.0%
Belgium	55.0%	45.0%	100.0%
Spain	54.4%	45.6%	100.0%
Greece	53.4%	46.6%	100.0%
Average	53.0%	47.0%	100.0%
Slovakia	52.7%	47.3%	100.0%
Lithuania	51.1%	48.9%	100.0%
Poland	49.3%	50.7%	100.0%
Estonia	48.3%	51.7%	100.0%
Croatia	45.4%	54.6%	100.0%
Cyprus	44.7%	55.3%	100.0%
Ukraine	44.5%	55.5%	100.0%
Latvia	40.9%	59.1%	100.0%
Romania	40.7%	59.3%	100.0%
Czech Republic	39.7%	60.3%	100.0%
Kosovo	37.5%	62.5%	100.0%
North Macedonia	36.6%	63.4%	100.0%
Montenegro	36.1%	63.9%	100.0%
Hungary	33.5%	66.5%	100.0%
Bosnia Herzegovina	33.0%	67.0%	100.0%
Albania	32.8%	67.2%	100.0%
Serbia	32.5%	67.5%	100.0%
Bulgaria	32.4%	67.6%	100.0%

improve (IRIS, 2022)

Do you think that research integrity policies help to improve the quality of your research?

Rank-ordered by 'Always/mostly'

	Seen, not answered	Missing	Always improve the quality of my research	Mostly improve the quality of my research	Always/mostly	Sometimes improve the quality of my research	Rarely improve the quality of my research	Never improve the quality of my research	Rarely/Never	Total
Portugal	0.8%	9.7%	20.2%	30.6%	25.4%	22.6%	12.5%	3.6%	8.1%	100%
Spain	1.1%	7.9%	15.2%	27.5%	21.4%	27.8%	16.4%	4.1%	10.3%	100%
Greece	1.3%	8.7%	12.6%	28.0%	20.3%	31.4%	14.7%	3.4%	9.1%	100%
IRIS average	1.1%	8.8%	16.0%	28.7%	22.4%	27.3%	14.5%	3.7%	9.1%	100%
France	1.4%	8.0%	11.3%	22.6%	17.0%	25.5%	21.5%	9.7%	15.6%	100%
Germany	1.6%	8.3%	6.7%	23.6%	15.2%	30.7%	21.8%	7.2%	14.5%	100%
UK	1.0%	8.7%	7.4%	20.8%	14.1%	30.1%	22.5%	9.4%	16.0%	100%
Denmark	0.9%	8.5%	5.9%	21.6%	13.8%	29.0%	25.6%	8.5%	17.1%	100%

mtvtrstpub (IRIS, 2022)

And now, how motivating would each of the following factors be in encouraging you to adhere to formal research integrity procedures? -- More trust in my research by the general public

Rank-ordered by 'Very/Extremely'

	Seen, not answered	Missing	Not at all motivating	Somewhat motivating	Not at all/Somewhat	Fairly motivating	Very motivating	Extremely motivating	Very/Extremely	Total
Portugal	3.3%	18.9%	3.1%	5.1%	4.1%	14.1%	31.3%	24.2%	27.8%	100%
Spain	4.7%	17.6%	2.6%	6.5%	4.6%	16.8%	31.3%	20.4%	25.9%	100%
IRIS average	4.4%	18.0%	4.9%	7.6%	6.3%	16.4%	27.9%	20.8%	24.4%	100%
UK	3.3%	17.0%	6.8%	8.5%	7.7%	16.3%	25.9%	22.1%	24.0%	100%
Greece	5.7%	18.7%	3.1%	7.8%	5.5%	17.4%	28.5%	18.8%	23.7%	100%
Denmark	4.0%	18.8%	6.0%	8.1%	7.1%	15.8%	26.6%	20.6%	23.6%	100%
France	4.3%	17.2%	7.3%	8.2%	7.8%	16.4%	25.5%	21.1%	23.3%	100%
Germany	5.5%	17.8%	5.7%	8.8%	7.3%	17.9%	26.0%	18.3%	22.2%	100%

Error margins in Eurobarometer surveys, assuming that N=1000 (Source: EB516 report).

Statistical Margins due to the sampling process
(at the 95% level of confidence)

various sample sizes are in rows

various observed results are in columns

	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%	35%	40%	45%	50%	
	95%	90%	85%	80%	75%	70%	65%	60%	55%	50%	
N=50	6,0	8,3	9,9	11,1	12,0	12,7	13,2	13,6	13,8	13,9	N=50
N=500	1,9	2,6	3,1	3,5	3,8	4,0	4,2	4,3	4,4	4,4	N=500
N=1000	1,4	1,9	2,2	2,5	2,7	2,8	3,0	3,0	3,1	3,1	N=1000
N=1500	1,1	1,5	1,8	2,0	2,2	2,3	2,4	2,5	2,5	2,5	N=1500
N=2000	1,0	1,3	1,6	1,8	1,9	2,0	2,1	2,1	2,2	2,2	N=2000
N=3000	0,8	1,1	1,3	1,4	1,5	1,6	1,7	1,8	1,8	1,8	N=3000
N=4000	0,7	0,9	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,4	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	N=4000
N=5000	0,6	0,8	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,3	1,4	1,4	1,4	N=5000
N=6000	0,6	0,8	0,9	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,3	1,3	N=6000
N=7000	0,5	0,7	0,8	0,9	1,0	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,2	1,2	N=7000
N=7500	0,5	0,7	0,8	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	N=7500
N=8000	0,5	0,7	0,8	0,9	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,1	1,1	1,1	N=8000
N=9000	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,9	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	N=9000
N=10000	0,4	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,0	N=10000
N=11000	0,4	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	N=11000
N=12000	0,4	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	N=12000
N=13000	0,4	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9	N=13000
N=14000	0,4	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	N=14000
N=15000	0,3	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	N=15000
	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%	35%	40%	45%	50%	
	95%	90%	85%	80%	75%	70%	65%	60%	55%	50%	

7 Appendix B – List of identified survey sources

Respondents	Country	Survey Name	Year(s)	Author/ Organisation/ Institution
Citizens	International	Eurobarometer	1989-2021	European Commission
Citizens	International	European Values Study	1981-2017	European Value Systems Study Group (EVSSG)
Citizens	International	World Values Study	1981-2022 (7 waves)	World Values Survey Association (WVSA)
Citizens	International	European Social Survey	2002-2020	ESS ERIC
Citizens	International	Wellcome Global Monitor	2018; 2020	Wellcome
Citizens	International	International Science Survey	2019-2020	Pew Research Center
Citizens	International	TRESCA	2021	TRESCA project
Citizens	International	HOPE	2020-2022	HOPE project - Michael Bang Pedersen
Citizens	International	YouGov	2020-2022	YouGov
Citizens	International	Maintaining trust during the COVID-19 pandemic	2020-2021	Eurofound
Citizens	Denmark	Gallup survey	2007-2011-2014	TNS Gallup
Citizens	Denmark	Operate 2020	2020	IDA
Citizens	Denmark	Folk og Forskning	1997-2000	Analyseinstitut for Forskning
Citizens	Denmark	Befolkningsmaling 2017	2017	YouGov
Citizens	France	Enquête Science	1972, 1982, 1989, 1994, 2001	Bon, Frédéric (IEP Paris) (1972 & 1982) Boy, Daniel (IEP Paris) (1989-2001)
Citizens	France	Image de la science	2007, 2011	Boy, Daniel (IEP Paris)
Citizens	France	La confiance des français dans la science	2019	Enquête Harris interactive
Citizens	France	Baromètre COVID	2020	Datacovid - Boy-Dubois

Respondents	Country	Survey Name	Year(s)	Author/ Organisation/ Institution
Citizens	France	Attitudes des populations face au COVID-19	2020	Cevipof - SciencesPo
Citizens	France	Attitudes des français à l'égard de la science	2020	Fondation Hulot pour la nature et l'homme
Citizens	France	Science et société	2020	Institut Sapiens
Citizens	France	Enquête Science	2021	Bauer, Dubois, Hervois
Citizens	France	Science et société	2022	Institut Sapiens
Citizens	France	Information et engagement climatique	2022	Fondation Descartes
Citizens	France	Baromètre de l'esprit critique	2022	Universcience
Citizens	France	La mésinformation scientifique des jeunes à l'heure des réseaux sociaux	2023	Fondation Jean Jaurès
Citizens	Germany	Wissenschaftsbarometer	annually since 2014	WiD
Citizens	Germany	Technikradar	bi-annually since 2018, 2020, 2022	Körper-Stiftung/acatech
Citizens	Greece	Mental Health in the post-COVID-19 era	Ongoing	UNICEF Greece, Greek Ministry of Education and Religion
Citizens	Greece	Public opinion regarding the COVID-19 pandemic	2020	Interview
Citizens	Greece	Nationwide research for climate change	Jun 22	dianeosis
Citizens	Greece	Nationwide research of the public opinion regarding the COVID-19 pandemic	Nov 21	dianeosis
Citizens	Portugal	Public perceptions about COVID-19	2020 (two waves of data)	Entradas et al. ISCTE
Citizens	Portugal	Relatório do Inquérito à Cultura Científica dos Portugueses: 2000	1999/2000	Ministério da Ciência e da Tecnologia. Observatório das Ciências e das Tecnologias
Citizens	Portugal	Públicos da Ciência em Portugal	2000	Iscte (to Fundação Gulbenkian Ciencia)

Respondents	Country	Survey Name	Year(s)	Author/ Organisation/ Institution
Citizens	Portugal	Relatório do Inquérito à Cultura Científica dos Portugueses: 1996/1997	1996/1997	Ministério da Ciência e da Tecnologia. Observatório das Ciências e das Tecnologias
Citizens	Spain	Encuesta de Percepción Social de la Ciencia	2020, 2018, 2016, 2014, 2012, 2010, 2008, 2006, 2004, 2002	FECYT (Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología)
Citizens	Spain	Desinformación científica en España	2022	FECYT (Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología)
Citizens	Spain	Cultura Científica Empresarial / Scientific Culture at Enterprises	2016	SCE Project
Citizens	UK	UK Research and Innovation Trust in Science Tracker	2020	Ipsos MORI
Citizens	UK	YouGov COVID survey	2020 & 2021	YouGov
Citizens	UK	A crisis in trust?	2010	Ipsos MORI
Citizens	UK	Uptake of the COVID-19 vaccine	2021	Ipsos MORI
Citizens	UK	Ipsos MORI Issues Index	2022	Ipsos MORI
Citizens	UK	Corona Poll (Adults)	2020	OnePoll
Citizens	UK	Corona Poll 2 (14-18 year-olds)	2020	OnePoll
Citizens	UK	Trust in GPs: A review of the literature and analyses of the GP/patient survey data	2014	National Centre for Research Methods
Citizens	UK	Veracity Index	2020-2022	Ipsos MORI
Scientists	International	International Research Integrity Survey (IRIS)	2021	SOPs4RI project
Scientists	International	MoRRI	2014-2018	MoRRI project
Scientists	International	Super-MoRRI	ongoing	SUPER MoRRI project

Respondents	Country	Survey Name	Year(s)	Author/ Organisation/ Institution
Scientists	International	MORE-PE	2017-2018	MORE-PE project
Scientists	Denmark (and a few respondents from elsewhere)	PRINT survey	2018	Jesper Schneider et al.
Scientists	France	Enquête sur la responsabilité sociale des scientifiques	2007	Boy, Daniel
Scientists	France	L'intégrité scientifique et l'éthique de la recherche à l'épreuve de la crise COVID-19	2022	Dubois, Michel
Scientists	Germany	Perspectives on Science Communication	2021	WiD, NaWik, DZHW
Scientists	Germany	Wissenschaftsbefragung	2010, 2016, 2019	DZHW
Scientists	Greece	The new Greek law for the operation of Research Ethics and Deontology Committees: context and challenges	2017	RNanoLab (NTUA)
Scientists	Greece	Greek institutional Research Ethics and Deontology Committees: experiences from the first three years of operation	2021	RNanoLab (NTUA)
Scientists	Portugal	A comunidade científica portuguesa nos finais do século XX: comportamentos, atitudes e expectativas	1995	Jorge Correia Jesuíno; Lígia Amâncio; Patrícia Ávila; Graca Carapineiro; António Firmino da Costa; Fernando Luís Machado; et al.
Scientists	Portugal	FCT researchers	2016	Marta Entradas, et al.